

Energy system model structure and parameters

“Potential-Risk and No-Regret Options for Urban Energy System Design - A Sensitivity Analysis”

May, 2023

Preface

This document contains explanations of the energy system model structure, as well as considered model parameters of the following study:

*“Potential-Risk and No-Regret Options for Urban Energy System
Design - A Sensitivity Analysis”*

The development of this document is an ongoing process and was initiated for the creation of an energy system model within the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF)-funded project “RessourcenPlan im Quartier (R2Q)”. Accordingly, some structural elements and model parameters were adopted, others were updated. The following persons have contributed to the development of this and previous versions:

Christian Klemm^{1,2}
christian.klemm@fh-muenster.de

Janik Budde¹
janik.budde@fh-muenster.de

Gregor Becker¹
gregor.becker@fh-muenster.de

Jan N. Tockloth¹
jan.tockloth@fh-muenster.de

Peter Vennemann¹
vennemann@fh-muenster.de

¹Department of Energy, Building Services and Environmental Engineering, Münster University of Applied Sciences, Münster, Germany

²Department of Energy and Environmental Management, Europa-Universität Flensburg, Flensburg, Germany

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of the BMBF (grant number 033W102).

Document Versions

Date	Study Name	Reference
2022-08-08	Urban energy system modeling within the R2Q project	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6974402
2022-08-16	Model-based run-time and memory optimization for a mixed-use multi-energy system model with high spatial resolution	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6997547
2022-11-25	Energy system modeling for a medium sized neighborhood	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7360806
2023-02-07	Structure of Urban Energy System Models	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7615332
2023-05-04	Potential-Risk and No-Regret Options for Urban Energy System Design - A Sensitivity Analysis	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10477476

Contents

1	Model Profile	4
2	Model Structure	5
2.1	Sub-systems	7
2.1.1	Electrical components	7
2.1.2	Heat components	8
2.1.3	Sector coupling components	11
2.1.4	Other relationships	13
2.2	Main System	13
2.2.1	Electric components	13
2.2.2	Heat components	14
3	Model parameters	19
3.1	General interrelationships and calculation basis	23
3.1.1	Annualized capital costs	23
3.1.2	Linearization of fix costs	23
3.1.3	Considered emissions	24
3.1.4	General simplifications	24
3.2	Component specific calculations and relationships	24
3.2.1	Sources	24
3.2.2	Sinks	27
3.2.3	Transformers	36
3.2.4	Storages	44
3.2.5	Links	48
3.3	Weather data	51
	Acronyms	54
	Acknowledgements	54
	References	55

1 Model Profile

Table 1.1: Model profile due to energy system model classification scheme by [1].

Category	Property	Details
Methodology	optimization	multi-objective ϵ -constraint optimization [2]
Assessment Criteria	multi-criteria	financial costs, greenhouse gas emissions
Analytical Approach	bottom-up	
Mathematical Approach	(mixed-integer) linear programming	
Reusability	open	all methods and input parameters are available under open source licenses
Challenges	data quality and transparency, assumptions	
Geographic Coverage	local	
Spatial Resolution	house sharp / block sharp	
Temporal Resolution	hourly, fixed resolution	
Time Horizon	one year	data of the year 2012 (see Sec. 3.3)
Sectoral Coverage	multi-sectoral	electricity, heat, fossil fuels, hydrogen
Demand Sectors	multi-sectoral	residential, commercial, industrial
Technical Coverage	electricity import, natural gas import, hydrogen import, photovoltaic system, solar thermal collector, gas heating system, central gas heating plant, district heat house station, electric radiator, combined heat and power plant, heat pumps, electrolysis, methanization, fuel cell, central thermal storage, building heat storage, battery storage, hydrogen storage, natural gas storage, electricity export, heat demand, electricity demand, building heat system, district heat network	
Demand Side Management	building insulation	outer wall, step roof, flat roof, windows upper ceiling, basement ceiling
Change of Properties	static	

2 Model Structure

The model is designed according to the model structure of the Spreadsheet Energy System Model Generator (SESMG) [3], which is based on the Open Energy Modelling Framework (oemof) [4]. Following the logic of these modeling tools, a distinction is made between the following system components:

- **sources:** “Sources represent the provision of energy. This can either be the exploitation of an energy source (e.g., gas storage reservoir or solar energy, no energy source in physical sense), or the simplified energy import from adjacent energy systems.” [3]
- **sinks:** “Sinks represent either energy demands within the energy system or energy exports to adjacent systems.” [3]
- **transformers:** “Transformers are components with one or more input flows, which are transformed to one or more output flows. Transformers may be power plants [or] energy transforming processes (e.g., electrolysis, heat pumps)” [3]
- **storages:** “Storages are connected to a bus and can store energy from this bus and return it to a later point in time.” [3]
- **links:** “Links can be used to connect two buses or to display transport losses of networks. Links are not represented by a separate oemof class, they are rather represented by transformers. In order to map a loss-free connection between two buses, an efficiency of 1 is used.” [3]
- **buses:** “The modeling framework oemof does not allow direct connections between components. Instead, they must always be connected with a bus. The bus in turn can be connected to other components, so that energy can be transported via the bus. Buses can have any number of incoming and outgoing flows. Buses can not directly be connected with each other. They do not consider any conversion processes or losses.” [3]

The different components are combined into an energy system using the mathematical graph theory, where the nodes are the different components and the edges are energy flows between these components. The different components are represented in the following by the symbols shown in Fig. 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Model component symbols.

According to this model logic, the model structure for the investigated area is shown in Fig. 2.2. The model structure contains a main system and several sub-systems. For reasons of clarity, only one sub-system is shown here, but any number of additional sub-systems can be connected to the main system in the same way.

In the following, the structure and connection of the individual components of the *Sub-systems* and *Main System* are explained.

Figure 2.2: Schematic representation of an urban energy system model, containing one sub-system. Legend according to Fig. 2.1.

2.1 Sub-systems

2.1.1 Electrical components

Electricity distribution system: The electric distribution within sub-systems is considered to be loss free. Therefore, the sub-system electricity bus represents the entire distribution system.

Figure 2.3: Schematic representation of a sub-systems modeled electricity distribution system. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1.

Electricity demand: The electricity demand sink is directly connected to the sub-system electricity bus.

Figure 2.4: Schematic representation of a sub-systems modeled electricity demand. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1.

Electricity import: Due to different prices for electricity imports, the sub-system electricity import source is connected to every sub-systems electricity bus.

Figure 2.5: Schematic representation of a sub-systems modeled electricity import. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1.

Photovoltaic system: The photovoltaic (PV) collector source component includes the technical equipment of the collector and the inverter. Electricity provided can either directly be used in the sub-system or be exported. In order to ensure that the set export/excess price is only taken into account for electricity provided by the PV system, a separate PV electricity bus is necessary, which in turn is connected to the sub-system electricity bus by a directed link [5].

Figure 2.6: Schematic representation of a sub-systems modeled photovoltaic system. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1.

Battery storage: Storage technologies are directly connected to the sub-system electricity bus. In this way, the electricity of all supply technologies can be stored.

Figure 2.7: Schematic representation of a sub-systems modeled battery storage. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1.

2.1.2 Heat components

Heat distribution system: In order to be able to take losses in the sub-systems internal heat distribution system into account, the system is divided into two buses. All components before distribution loss get relevant are connected to the sub-system (final energy) heat bus. This bus contains heat energy in a transfer medium (water) and thus final energy (see definitions in [6]). Via a link distribution losses of the heat distribution system and radiators are taken into account, the energy is transferred to the sub-system (effective energy) heat bus. This bus includes effective energy (see definitions in [6]) that can serve the *heat demand*.

Figure 2.8: Schematic representation of a sub-systems modeled heat distribution system. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1.

Heat demand: The sub-systems heat demand is connected to the sub-system (effective energy) heat bus.

Figure 2.9: Schematic representation of a sub-systems modeled heat demand. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1.

Building insulation: Renovation measures are reducing the *heat demand* through improvements in building U-values. Since oemof does not provide investments in such components, the SESMG incorporates this by implementing a renovation measure source that feeds exactly the energy amount into the sub-system (effective energy) heat bus that is consumed less in real terms as a result of the measure by the heat demand sink. During the post-processing, the energy balance is corrected by the amount of energy fed into the system.

Figure 2.10: Schematic representation of a sub-systems modeled building insulation. Symbols according to fig:legend.

Gas heating system: Gas heating systems consist of several components. A gas heating transformer converts natural gas into heat and is connected to the sub-system (final energy) heat bus. The required gas is supplied by the natural gas import source via the sub-system natural gas bus.

Figure 2.11: Schematic representation of a sub-systems modeled gas heating system. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1.

Solar thermal system: Solar thermal systems consist of several components. Solar energy is supplied by the solar source, which is connected via the solar bus to the solar thermal collector. There, while consuming electricity, which is provided by the sub-system electricity bus, usable heat is provided to the sub-system (final energy) heat bus.

Figure 2.12: Schematic representation of a sub-systems modeled solar thermal system. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1

Thermal storage: It is assumed that thermal storage is installed centrally in buildings, close to the heat-producing technology. The thermal storage is thus connected to the sub-system (final energy) heat bus. After withdrawal, the heat can be transported to the end user via the *heat distribution system* (paragraph 2.1.2). The thermal storage can thus temporarily store provided final energy (e.g., provided by the *gas heating system*) but not effective energy (e.g., provided by electric radiators, referring to energy definitions in [6]).

Figure 2.13: Schematic representation of a sub-systems modeled thermal storage. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1.

2.1.3 Sector coupling components

Heat pumps: Different types of heat pumps are identically integrated into the model as sub-systems. The heat source (e.g., ground or air) is connected to the heat pump transformer via a source bus. The electricity required for operation is obtained from the sub-system heat pump electricity bus. This enables the import/shortage of electricity at a special heat pump tariff,

such as exists in Germany. In addition, electricity can also be obtained from the sub-system electricity bus via a directed link.

Figure 2.14: Schematic representation of a sub-systems modeled heat pumps. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1.

electric heating system The electric heating transformer converts electrical energy of the sub-system electricity bus into heat. Assuming that the electric heaters provide heat directly in the form of effective energy (referring to the definitions in [6]) – so the heat distribution system of the building is not used – the **electric heating**-transformer is connected directly to the sub-system (effective energy) heat bus.

Figure 2.15: Schematic representation of a sub-systems modeled electric heating system. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1 [Abbildung aktualisieren](#)

2.1.4 Other relationships

Surface concurrency: The design of a particular system may preclude the design of another technology due to consumed resources (e.g., available space). In this model, competition for space occurs between *photovoltaic systems* and *solar thermal systems*, both of which are mounted on roofs. A constraint is therefore used in this model to limit the dimension of these systems to the available space. The ratio of the added systems is not specified.

2.2 Main System

2.2.1 Electric components

Electricity distribution system: As with the *electricity distribution system* of sub-systems the electricity distribution within the district is considered to be loss free, and is therefore represented by a single district electricity bus.

Figure 2.16: Schematic representation of the main-systems modeled electricity distribution system. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1.

Exchange of electricity between sub-systems: In order to enable the exchange of electricity between individual subsystems (e.g., in the context of a local energy market) one directed link per direction is implemented between the respective sub-system electricity bus and the district electricity bus.

The division into two links (instead of one undirected link) is necessary to avoid a duplication of transmission costs (e.g., due to network charges, see Sec. 3.2) when transmitting between two sub-systems. For this reason, only costs for transmission from the sub-system electricity bus to the district electricity bus are applied. No costs are applied in the reverse direction.

Figure 2.17: Schematic representation of the main-systems modeled exchange of electricity between sub-systems. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1.

Central battery storage: As with *battery storage* of sub-systems, in the district electricity system, electricity storage technologies are connected to the district electricity bus. In this way, the electricity of all supply technologies can be stored.

Figure 2.18: Schematic representation of the main-systems modeled central battery storage. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1.

2.2.2 Heat components

District heating network: The district heating network consists of a series of district head node buses connected by links. Each bus represents a node or a bend of the district heating network. Accordingly, the links represent the pipelines connecting the individual node buses. In Fig. 2.19 a network consisting of two node buses and a pipeline is shown as an example. In the actual model, the heat network consists of several buses and links.

The transfer of heat to sub-systems is done via district heat house station transformer, which is connected to the district heating network via the corresponding spatially located node-bus. This transformer represents a heat exchanger, which transfers the heat to the sub-system heat system.

Figure 2.19: Schematic representation of a modeled *district heating network*. Legend according to Fig. 2.1.

Central heat storage: Central heat storages are directly connected to the district heating network via the corresponding spatially located node-bus.

Figure 2.20: Schematic representation of the main-systems modeled central heat storage. Symbols according to Fig. 2.1

2.2.2.1 Sector coupling components

Combined heat and power plants: Combined heat and power (CHP) plants generate both heat and electricity from natural gas. Natural gas is provided by importing natural gas (central natural gas import source) through the district natural gas bus for the natural gas CHP transformer. The heat output is connected to the district heating network via the corresponding spatially located node-bus.

The electricity is delivered (similar to the distribution of electricity from *photovoltaic system* in sub-systems) to a separate natural gas CHP electricity bus. In this way there is the possibility to use the produced electricity in different ways. In this case, export is possible via the central CHP electricity export sink or transfer to the district electricity bus.

Analogously, other combined heat and power plants (e.g., operated with biogas) can be included.

Figure 2.21: Schematic representation of a modeled CHP. Legend according to Fig. 2.1

Central heat pump: Analogous to *heat pumps* in sub-systems, a heat source (e.g., soil water) is connected to the heat pump transformer via a source bus. The electricity required for operation is obtained from the district heat pump electricity bus. This enables the import/shortage of electricity at a special heat pump tariff, such as exists in Germany. In addition, electricity can also be obtained from the sub-system electricity bus via a directed link. The heat output is connected to the district heating network via the corresponding spatially located node-bus.

Figure 2.22: Schematic representation of a modeled central heat pump. Legend according to Fig. 2.1.

Central hydrogen system The central hydrogen system consist of several components and technologies. Hydrogen can either be imported or produced with the electrolysis transformer using electricity from the district electricity bus. The available hydrogen within the “h2 bus”, used by the methanization transformer, or used by the fuel cell transformer. The fuel cell transformer uses hydrogen to produce heat for a district heating network bus and electricity for the district electricity bus. The methanization transformer converts hydrogen into natural gas, which in turn can be stored in a natural gas storage or passed to the natural gas buses of central natural gas CHPs or sub-systems natural gas buses of natural gas heating systems.

Figure 2.23: Schematic representation of a modeled central hydrogen system. Legend according to Fig. 2.1.

3 Model parameters

For different types of components, described in Sec. 2, the following parameters are required for the modeling:

- **variable costs:** costs (in €) incurred per kWh of converted/provided energy
- **periodical costs:** costs (in €) incurred per year regardless of the amount of converted/provided energy
- **variable emissions:** carbon dioxide (CO₂) emission equivalents (in g) incurred per kWh of converted/provided energy
- **periodical emissions:** CO₂ emission equivalents (in g) incurred per year regardless of the amount of converted/provided energy
- **efficiency:** efficiency of energy conversion/provision of a component
- **further parameters:** some components require further parameters, which are described individually

Tab. 3.1 shows a compact overview of the model parameters used. In Sec. 3.1 and Sec. 3.2 the calculation methods and references of the individual values are presented in detail.

Table 3.1: Model Parameters. Values without references have been calculated or reasonably estimated. The procedure used in each case is explained in the following sections of this document. For column, containing two values, the first value refers to the components electric output, the second to the thermal output.

technology	specification	var. costs	per. costs	var. emiss.	per. emiss.	efficiency	further parameters
SOURCES		€/kWh	€/(kW · a)	g CO ₂ /kWh	g CO ₂ /(kW · a)		
electricity import	residential	0.3122 [7]	0	366 [8]	0	1	
	heat pumps	0.22 [9]	0	366 [8]	0	1	
	commercial	0.2303 [10]	0	366 [8]	0	1	
	industrial	0.1654 [10]	0	366 [8]	0	1	
natural gas import	residential	0.0629 [11]	0	0	0	1	
	commercial	0.0452 [12]	0	0	0	1	
	industrial	0.0253 [12]	0	0	0	1	
hydrogen import		0.1562 [13]	0	44 [13]	0	1	
photovoltaic system		0	95	27 [14]	0	modeled	albedo = 0.18 [15], individual: latitude, longitude, altitude, azimuth, tilt
solar thermal collector		0	75	12 [14]	0	modeled	individual: latitude, longitude, altitude, azimuth, tilt
TRANSFORMERS		€/kWh	€/(kW · a)	g CO ₂ /kWh	g CO ₂ /(kW · a)		
gas heating system		0	110	232 [14]	0	0.92 [16]	
central gas heating plant		0	13	264 [14]	0	0.92 [16]	
district heat house station		0	86	0	0	0.98 [17]	
electric radiator		0	23	0	7136	1	
combined heat and power plant	natural gas	0	129	347/225	0	0.375/0.575	
	biogas	0	130	140/97	0	0.390/0.560	
heat pumps	ASHP (decentral)	0	137	0	8544	modeled	
	ASHP (central)	0	59	0	8544	modeled	
	GCHP (decentral)	0	142	0	8544	modeled	
	GCHP (central)	0	40	0	8544	modeled	
	GWHP	0	197	0	8544	modeled	
	SWHP	0	72	0	8544	modeled	
electrolysis		0	77	1.3 [18]	0	0.785	
fuell cell		0	255	10	0	0.40 / 0.50 [19]	
STORAGES		€/kWh	€/(kWh · a)	g CO ₂ /kWh	g CO ₂ /(kWh · a)		
central thermal storage		0	3	0	743 [20]	0.98 [21]	additionally 3 % losses per day [21], max. capacity = 0, min. capacity = 1, capacity inflow = 0.25 [22], capacity outflow = 0.25 [22]
building heat storage		0	4	0	604	0.98	losses = 0.2 %/h [23], max. capacity = 0, min. capacity = 1, capacity inflow = 1 [23], capacity outflow = 1 [23]

Table 3.1: Model Parameters. Values without references have been calculated or reasonably estimated. The procedure used in each case is explained in the following sections of this document. For column, containing two values, the first value refers to the components electric output, the second to the thermal output.

technology	specification	var. costs	per. costs	var. emiss.	per. emiss.	efficiency	further parameters
battery storage	decentral	0	89	0	3 960 [24]	0.98 [25]	max. capacity = 1, min. capacity = 0.1, capacity inflow = 0.77, capacity outflow = 0.71, max. capacity = 19.5 kW [25]
	central	0	90	0	3 960 [24]	0.98 [25]	max. capacity = 1, min. capacity = 0.1, capacity inflow = 0.77, capacity outflow = 0.71 [25]
hydrogen storage		0	1	0	320 [26]	1 [27]	losses per day = 0.78 %/d , max. capacity = 1, min. capacity = 0, capacity inflow = 1 [27], capacity outflow = 1 [27]
natural gas storage		0	1	0	320	1	losses per day = 0.78 %/d , max. capacity = 1, min. capacity = 0, capacity inflow = 1 [27], capacity outflow = 1 [27]
SINKS		€/kWh	€/(kW · a)	g CO ₂ /kWh	g CO ₂ /(kW · a)		
electricity export	rooftop PV system	-0.0683	0	-27 [14]	0	1	
	natural gas CHP	-0.0682	0	-347	0	1	
	biogas CHP	-0.128 [28]	0	-140	0	1	
LINKS		€/kWh	€/(kW · a)	g CO ₂ /kWh	g CO ₂ /(kW · a)		
building heat system		0	0	0	0	1	
district heat network	DN20	0	64	0	204	modeled	
	DN25	0	65	0	244	modeled	
	DN32	0	69	0	304	modeled	
	DN40	0	72	0	376	modeled	
	DN50	0	81	0	472	modeled	
	DN65	0	88	0	629	modeled	
	DN80	0	101	0	801	modeled	
	DN100	0	125	0	1056	modeled	
	DN125	0	150	0	1412	modeled	
	DN150	0	181	0	1812	modeled	
	DN200	0	215	0	2742	modeled	
DN250	0	288	0	3844	modeled		
electricity exchange		0.1391	0	0	0	1	
INSULATION		€/kWh	€/(kW · a)	g CO ₂ /kWh	g CO ₂ /(kW · a)		
building insulation	outer wall	0	6.08	0	216	–	U=0.20-0.24 [TobiasLoga.2015] W/m ² /K

Table 3.1: Model Parameters. Values without references have been calculated or reasonably estimated. The procedure used in each case is explained in the following sections of this document. For column, containing two values, the first value refers to the components electric output, the second to the thermal output.

technology	specification	var. costs	per. costs	var. emiss.	per. emiss.	efficiency	further parameters	
	step roof	0	9.35	0	286	–	U=0.24-0.45 [TobiasLoga.2015]	W/m ² /K
	flat roof	0	7.14	0	286	–	U=0.18-0.24 [TobiasLoga.2015]	W/m ² /K
	windows	0	21.9	0	2 400	–	U=0.70-0.95 [TobiasLoga.2015]	W/m ² /K

3.1 General interrelationships and calculation basis

This section describes the calculation bases of individual parameters. Interrelationships applicable to all components are presented.

3.1.1 Annualized capital costs

We consider annualized capital costs and annual operation costs as periodical costs (Eq. 3.1 to Eq. 3.3).

$$C_a = C_{O_a} + C_{cap_a} \quad (3.1)$$

$$C_a = C_{O_a} + C_I \cdot \frac{i(i+1)^y}{(i+1)^y - 1} \quad (3.2)$$

$$C_a = C_{O_a} + C_I \cdot A \quad (3.3)$$

C_a	annual costs
C_{O_a}	annual operation costs
C_{cap_a}	annualized capital costs
C_I	investment costs
i	rate of interest
y	component lifetime
A	annuity

In this sheet, a interest rate i of 4 % is chosen.

Operating costs are often given as a relationship to investment costs. In these cases the annual operation costs C_{O_a} are calculated according to the VDI directive 2067-1 [29] using the operation cost factor f_{O_a} .

$$C_{O_a} = C_I \cdot f_{O_a} \quad (3.4)$$

C_{O_a}	annual operation costs
C_I	investment costs
f_{O_a}	operation cost factor

3.1.2 Linearization of fix costs

Sometimes investment and operation costs are only conditionally dependent on the exact capacity of a component. In order to be able to take these into account in linear programming, the following formula is used:

$$c_a = \frac{C_a}{P_D} \quad (3.5)$$

c_a	specific annual costs
C_a	absolute annual costs
P_D	typical design capacity

For a more accurate determination of the value, an iterative optimization process may be considered: After an initial design of the component capacity, the value of the typical design capacity P_D can be replaced and the component can then be actuated with that. The process can be repeated as often as necessary.

3.1.3 Considered emissions

We account for the greenhouse gas (GHG) emission scopes listed in Tab. 3.2. Terms based on definitions of the World Resource Institute [30] and adapted for the purpose of analyzing urban energy systems.

Table 3.2: Considered GHG emission scopes.

Scope	Definition
1	“Direct GHG emissions occur from sources that are [within the model domain,] for example, emissions from combustion in owned or controlled boilers, [...], etc.” [30].
2	“GHG emissions from the generation of [imported] electricity[, consumed within the model domain.]” “Scope 2 emissions physically occur at the facility where electricity is generated” [30]. For exported electricity a GHG emission credit is granted, accordingly.
3	“[GHG emissions of energy supply facilities which] occur from sources not owned or controlled” [30] within the model domain, e.g., for the production of photovoltaic modules.

Further determinations:

- For the accounting of emissions for energy supply technologies, cumulative emissions per kWh of energy converted (including production, installation, operation, ...) are used. Although in some cases a split into variable and periodic costs might be more accurate, we follow this approach in order to correctly account for the corresponding energy emissions in the case of energy exports (scope 2, Tab. 3.2). In addition, we want to apply a uniform procedure so that we also apply this procedure to energy supply technologies that do not provide export energy (e.g., solar thermal systems).
- Emissions from the combustion of fossil raw materials are taken into account at the point where they occur (e.g., at the gas heating system, at the CHP unit, etc.).

3.1.4 General simplifications

Building insulation: When considering the cost of additional building insulation, the initial state of the insulation is neglected. A cost value indicates how much it costs to insulate to a certain U-value when the original insulation is replaced by the new one. In real terms, the old insulation may be replaced by new insulation. In view of the lack of data on existing buildings and cost parameters, this simplification must be made.

Energy storages: The modeled storage systems allow for the consideration of operating energy only as storage losses. The consideration of, for example, electrical auxiliary energy of thermal storage is not possible.

Large facilities: For large components, such as central CHP units or storage facilities, only the costs of the technology are estimated, but not the costs for buildings, property, etc.

3.2 Component specific calculations and relationships

3.2.1 Sources

3.2.1.1 Electricity import

Variable costs: The values to be applied vary depending on the type of customer (residential, commercial, industrial) and sometimes separate tariffs are granted for the consumption of certain components (e.g., heat pumps). We take into account statistical values of variable costs, in which

average periodical costs (e.g., connection fee) are included. For residential buildings, electricity costs averaged 0.3122 €/kWh in 2021 [7].

Periodical costs: No periodical costs apply, since the connection fee is part of the variable costs consideration.

Variable/periodical emissions: A static value is taken into account. Real fluctuations due to volatile production changes are not taken into account. The variable emission value takes into account any incurred costs that are considered in the life cycle analysis. This is necessary to correctly account emissions from exported energy (Sec. 3.1.3).

3.2.1.2 Natural gas import

Variable costs: The values to be applied vary depending on the type of customer (residential, commercial, industrial). We take into account statistical values of variable costs, in which average periodic costs (e.g., connection fee) are included. For residential buildings, gas costs averaged 0.0629 €/kWh in 2021 [11].

Periodical costs: No periodical costs apply, since the connection fee is part of the variable costs consideration.

Variable/periodical emissions: The emissions generated for the provision of the gas are taken into account by life-cycle assessment at the point of use (e.g., Sec. 3.2.3.1).

3.2.1.3 Hydrogen import

Variable costs: The values to be applied vary depending on the type of customer (residential, commercial, industrial).

Periodical costs: No periodical costs apply, since the connection fee is part of the variable costs consideration.

Variable/periodical emissions: The emissions generated for the provision of the gas are taken into account by life-cycle assessment at the point of use (e.g., Sec. 3.2.3.8, Sec. 3.2.3.9).

3.2.1.4 Photovoltaic system

Variable costs: No variable costs apply.

Periodical costs: Periodical costs are calculated due to Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values of Tab. 3.3.

Table 3.3: Values for calculating periodical costs.

		value	unit	ref.
component lifetime	y	20	a	[31]
rate of interest	i	4	%	Sec. 3.1.1
operation costs factor	f_{O_a}	1.5	%/a	[31]
investment costs	C_I	1 070	€/kW	[32]

Variable/periodical emissions: We consider cumulative GHG emissions per kWh of electricity produced, according to the Global Emission Model of Integrated Systems (GEMIS) scenario “Solar-PV-multi-Rahmen-mit-Rack-DE-2020” [14].

Efficiency: Based on weather data and individual orientation of PV collectors. The PV system peak performance is assumed to be 0.19 kW/m^2 . This value was determined by comparing current modules on the German PV system market. Further specific plant parameters required for modeling are obtained automatically from the “SandiaMod” database [33] using the “feedinlib” [34]. The reference module “Panasonic VBHN235SA06B” and the reference inverter “ABB MICRO 0.25 I OUTD US 240 240V” are used.

Further parameters: For typical roofing materials, the albedo value ρ_S for weathered concrete is assumed to be 0.20 [15]. Parameters such as the maximum investment capacity (depending on the available space), the location of the PV system (longitude, latitude, altitude), as well as the orientation of the collectors (azimuth, tilt) are not standardizable and need to be defined individually. Solar potential registers often provide a good data basis (e.g., [35]). For the castle project the altitude was estimated to 75 m.

3.2.1.5 Solar thermal collector

Variable costs: No variable costs apply. Costs for electricity are taken into account via the corresponding electricity source.

Periodical costs: The periodical costs are calculated due to Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values of Tab. 3.4.

Table 3.4: Values for calculating periodical costs. All values were assumed for a flat plate collector.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	20	a		[29]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	846	€/kW	for a collector surface of 5 m^2 (660 €/m^2), Eq. 3.7	[36]
operation costs factor	f_{O_a}	1.5	%/a		[29]

Variable/periodical emissions: We consider cumulative GHG emissions per kWh of heat produced, according to the GEMIS scenario “SolarKollektor-Flach-DE-2020” [14]. Operating electricity is taken into account elsewhere in the model. No periodical emissions apply.

Efficiency: The efficiency is modeled, based on the sun irradiation and orientation of the collectors. The maximum thermal efficiency η_0 is assumed to be 0.78 for flat-plate collectors and vacuum tube collectors [37].

Using this efficiency the power specific costs can be calculated with Eq. 3.6.

$$C_I = \frac{C_{sqm}}{\eta_0} \quad (3.6)$$

C_I investment costs
 C_{sqm} area specific costs
 η_0 maximum thermal efficiency

Further parameters: Parameters such as the maximum investment capacity (depending on the available space), the location of the solar thermal system (longitude, latitude), as well as the orientation of the collectors (azimuth, tilt) are not standardizable and need to be defined

individually. Solar potential registers often provide a good data basis (e.g., [35]).

The peak performance of solar thermal collectors can be calculated with Eq. 3.7 [38]. An irradiance of $G_N = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$ can be assumed, based on standardized radiation spectrum AM1.5 for tests of PV systems [31]. This value is adopted here for solar thermal systems.

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{peak}} = \eta_0 \cdot G_N \cdot A \quad (3.7)$$

\dot{Q}_{peak}	peak performance
η_0	maximum thermal efficiency
G_N	irradiance
A	collector surface

$$\eta_C = \eta_0 - a_1 * \frac{T_{\text{inlet}} + \Delta T_n - T_{\text{amb}}}{G_N} - a_2 * \frac{(T_{\text{inlet}} + \Delta T_n - T_{\text{amb}})^2}{G_N} \quad (3.8)$$

η_C	collector efficiency
η_0	maximum thermal efficiency
T_{inlet}	inlet temperature
ΔT_n	difference between collector mean and inlet temperature
T_{amb}	ambient temperature
G_N	irradiance
a_1	linear thermal loss factor
a_2	quadratic thermal loss factor

According [37] the thermal loss factors can be assumed as $a_1 = 3.8 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K})$ and $a_2 = 0.015 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K}^2)$. The inlet temperature of the modules can usually be estimated to be $T_{\text{inlet}} = 40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and the difference ΔT_n between the inlet temperature T_{inlet} and the collectors mean temperature T_{mean} as 10 K^1 . Additionally an electric consumption of 2 % [39] and peripheral losses of 9 % [40] were used to calculate the solar thermal input.

3.2.2 Sinks

3.2.2.1 Electricity demand

The electricity demand varies in dependency of the consumer type. Following estimation methods are presented.

Electricity load profiles: Depending on the type of use of a building, different standard load profiles are used (Tab. 3.5).

¹Within this study temperatures of $T_{\text{inlet}} = 60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $\Delta T_n = 40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ were applied.

Table 3.5: Applied electric standard load profiles.

profile	consumer group	ref.
H0	households	[41]
G0	commercial general	[41]
G1	commercial on weeks between 8-18 hrs	[41]
G2	commercial with strong consumption in the evening	[41]
G3	commercial continuous	[41]
G4	shop/hairdresser	[41]
G5	bakery	[41]
G6	weekend operation	[41]
L0	agriculture general	[41]
L1	agriculture with dairy industry/animal breeding	[41]
L2	other agriculture	[41]
SL	street lights	[42]

Annual electricity demand (residential): The annual residential electricity demand can be estimated by the household size, with the values presented in Tab. 3.6.

Table 3.6: Typical electricity consumption of German households. Acronyms: single family building (SFB), multi family building (MFB).

household size (residents)	SFB in kWh/a	MFB in kWh/a	ref.
1	2 300	1 500	[43]
2	3 000	2 100	[44]
3	3 600	2 600	[45]
4	4 000	3 000	[46]
5	5 000	3 600	[47]

If the size of individual households is not known, the value is determined by a stochastic value. For Strünkede, for example, the distribution of household sizes (Tab. 3.7) can be used as a stochastic weighting.

Table 3.7: Distribution of household sizes in Strünkede (Herne, NRW, Germany) [48]

household size	households	share
1	1 779	0.442
2	1 253	0.311
3	515	0.128
4	300	0.074
≥ 5	181	0.045
total	4 028	1

Annual electricity demand (commercial): The annual electricity demand of commercial buildings can be estimated by the net floor area NFA [49] and the values listed in Tab. 3.8:

$$\text{NFA} = \text{GFA} \cdot \text{NF} \cdot f_{\text{NFA}} \quad (3.9)$$

NFA	net floor area
GFA	gross floor area
NF	number of floors
f_{NFA}	net-gross floor area ratio

$$E_{\text{elec}} = e_{\text{elec}} \cdot \text{NFA} \quad (3.10)$$

E_{elec}	annual electricity demand
e_{elec}	specific electricity demand (Tab. 3.8)
NFA	net floor area (Eq. 3.9)

Table 3.8: Statistical annual specific electricity demands e_{elec} and net-gross floor area ratios f_{NFA} of commercial buildings.

Type	e_{elec} kWh/(m ² · a)	ref.	f_{NFA}	ref.
Retail (Food)	378	[50]	0.90	assumption
Retail (Non-Food)	115	[51]	0.90	[50]
Office	17	[50]	0.85	[50]
School	10	[50]	0.89	[50]
Stable	3	[50]	0.90	[50]
Sports	17	[50]	0.91	[50]
Workshop	4	[50]	0.91	[50]
Restaurant	126	[50]	0.85	[50]
Hotel (Food)	83	[50]	0.91	[50]

Further notes:

- Retail (Food): [50] differentiate by total sales area. According to [52], the average sales areas of the large German food retail markets are in the range between 903 to 1 511 m². Therefore, we take the value for sales areas from 1 000 to 1 499 m² as the standard value. [51] estimates a comparable value in the same order of magnitude.
- Office: Assumed to the VDI directive 3807-2 category: “Administration buildings, standard technical equipment” [50].

3.2.2.2 Electricity export

The values to be applied depend on the technology used to supply the exported energy.

Variable costs (PV systems): In Germany, photovoltaic systems are granted a fixed rate of remuneration for feed-in in accordance with the Renewable Energies Act 2021 (EEG 2021). The remuneration is dependent on the location (e.g., roof), date of commissioning, and peak capacity. Tab. 3.9 lists the rates for PV systems installed on buildings (§ 48 para. 2 EEG 2021) and other PV systems (§ 48 para. 1 EEG 2021) installed in 2021 or later.

Table 3.9: Remuneration rates (ct/kWh) for roof-mounted PV systems according to the EEG 2021 [28, 53]. Applied values are highlighted.

commissioning	§ 48 para. 2 EEG 2021			§ 48 para. 1 EEG 2021
	≤10 kW	≤40 kW	≤100 kW	0 - 100 kW
from 01.01.2021	8.16	7.93	6.22	5.61
from 01.02.2021	8.04	7.81	6.13	5.53
from 01.03.2021	7.92	7.70	6.04	5.44
from 01.04.2021	7.81	7.59	5.95	5.36
from 01.05.2021	7.69	7.47	5.86	5.28
from 01.06.2021	7.58	7.36	5.77	5.20
from 01.07.2021	7.47	7.25	5.68	5.12
from 01.08.2021	7.36	7.15	5.60	5.05
from 01.09.2021	7.25	7.04	5.51	4.97
from 01.10.2021	7.14	6.94	5.43	4.89
from 01.11.2021	7.03	6.83	5.35	4.82
from 01.12.2021	6.93	6.73	5.27	4.75
from 01.01.2022	6.83	6.63	5.19	4.67

Based on the total output, this results in a mixed rate of remuneration. Plants receive the respective partial rates of remuneration $r_{\leq 10\text{kW}}$, $r_{10-40\text{kW}}$, and $r_{40-100\text{kW}}$ according to Tab. 3.9 in proportion to their total capacity [28]. The total rate of remuneration r is thus calculated as follows:

$$r = (r_{\leq 10\text{kW}} \cdot P_{\leq 10\text{kW}} + r_{10-40\text{kW}} \cdot P_{10-40\text{kW}} + r_{40-100\text{kW}} \cdot P_{40-100\text{kW}}) \frac{1}{P_{\text{total}}} \quad (3.11)$$

$r_{\leq 10\text{kW}}, r_{10-40\text{kW}}, r_{40-100\text{kW}}$	partial rate of remuneration
$P_{\leq 10\text{kW}}, P_{10-40\text{kW}}, P_{40-100\text{kW}}$	partial performance
P_{total}	total system (peak) performance

Accordingly, for example, for PV systems commissioned in January 2022, the following rates of remuneration (as listed in Tab. 3.9) are

$$\begin{aligned} r(P_{\text{ges}} = 10 \text{ kW}) &= 6.830 \text{ ct/kWh}, \\ r(P_{\text{ges}} = 40 \text{ kW}) &= 6.680 \text{ ct/kWh}, \text{ and} \\ r(P_{\text{ges}} = 100 \text{ kW}) &= 5.786 \text{ ct/kWh} \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

In this model, it is assumed for simplicity that all rooftop PV systems have a capacity below 10 kW, with regard to the export price calculation.

Variable costs (natural gas CHP): Due to the Combined Heat and Power Act 2020 (KWKG 2020) [54] a remuneration is granted, which is added to the regular electricity selling price. The remuneration rate and period is depending on the capacity of the CHP (Tab. 3.10).

Table 3.10: Remuneration rates granted due to § 7 para. 1 KWKG 2020 [54].

performance in kW	supplement in ct/kWh	duration in full load hours
≤ 50	8.0	60 000
51 - 100	6.0	30 000
101 - 250	5.0	30 000
250 - 2 000	4.4	30 000
> 2 000	3.1	30 000

The normalized excess cost value to be considered in models is calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{excess cost} = -\left(\frac{\text{FLH}_{\text{rem}}}{\text{FLH}_a \cdot y} \cdot r + p\right) \quad (3.13)$$

FLH_{rem}	remunerated full load hours
FLH_a	annual full load hours
y	component lifetime
r	remuneration rate
p	appraised selling price

Table 3.11: Values for calculating electricity export costs.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
remunerated full load hours	FLH_{rem}	30 000	h		[54]
annual full load hours	FLH_a	5 000	h/a		[55, 56]
component lifetime	y	15	a		[29]
remuneration rate	r	0.05	€/kWh		[54]
appraised selling price	p	0.0482	€/kWh	average spot price 06/2020-06/2021	[57]

Variable emissions: According to the defined emission balance (scope 2, Sec. 3.1.3), the emission quantity that was considered for production is credited for the export of electricity. Therefore, the respective negative variable emission value of the production technology is applied here.

3.2.2.3 Heat demand

Annual heat demand (residential): If the annual heat demand of the building is not known, it can be statistically determined, by using the following equation, as well as the values listed in Tab. 3.12. f_{NFA} for residential buildings is assumed to be 0.9.

$$E_{\text{heat}} = e_{\text{heat}} \cdot \text{NFA} \quad (3.14)$$

E_{heat}	annual heat demand
e'_{heat}	specific heat demand (Tab. 3.12)
NFA	net floor area (Eq. 3.9)

Table 3.12: Annual heat demand of residential buildings, depending on the year of construction and number of housing units [58].

year of construction	1 unit	2 units	3-6 units in kWh/(m ² · a)	7-12 units	>13 units
before 1918	247	238	212	182	169
1919-1948	254	236	211	178	153
1949-1978	236	219	192	166	140
1979-1990	175	168	155	152	118
1991-2000	131	127	127	114	101
2001-2008	83	88	80	76	69
since 2009	48	46	46	53	54

Often, the year of construction is not available, but statistical distributions of the construction dates within certain areas are, for example, given with the German census datasets [59]. In order to generate replacement values, weighted random values can be assigned to the individual buildings in accordance with the distribution of the construction years.

Table 3.13: Distribution of building construction years in Herne [59].

year of construction	number of buildings	share
before 1919	5 191	0.211
1919 - 1948	4 047	0.165
1949 - 1978	10 145	0.413
1979 - 1986	1 667	0.068
1987 - 1990	648	0.026
1991 - 1995	836	0.034
1996 - 2000	958	0.039
2001 - 2004	577	0.023
2005 - 2008	364	0.015
from 2009	147	0.006
total	24 580	1

Annual heat demand (commercial): The calculation is analogous to the determination of residential buildings, with the values from Tab. 3.14.

Table 3.14: Typical specific heat demands of commercial buildings.

year of construction	office	retail (food)	retail (non-food)	school	stable	sports	workshop	restau- rant	hotel (food)
	in kWh/(m ² · a)								
before 1918	138.3	275	153	100	80	130	82	200	189
1919-1949	148.0	275	153	100	80	130	82	200	189
1950-1964	149.8	275	153	100	80	130	82	200	189
1965-1977	152.6	275	153	100	80	130	82	200	189
1978-1989	136.3	275	153	100	80	130	82	200	189
1990-1994	125.4	275	153	100	80	130	82	200	189
1995-2002	110.0	275	153	100	80	130	82	200	189
since 2003	101.6	275	153	100	80	130	82	200	189
reference	[58]	[50]	[50]	[50]	[50]	[50]	[50]	[50]	[50]

Load profiles: Various load profile methods are used to distribute the annual demand over the individual time steps considered in the model. The methods applied are listed in Tab. 3.15.

Table 3.15: Heat standard load profiles given by German Association of Energy and Water Industries (BDEW) [60, 61].

profile	consumer group
EFH	SFB
MFH	MFB
GMK	metal and automotive
GHA	retail and wholesale
GKO	local authorities, credit institutions and insurance companies
GBD	other operational services
GGA	restaurants
GBH	accommodation
GWA	laundries, dry cleaning
GGB	horticulture
GBA	bakery
GPD	paper and printing
GMF	household-like business enterprises
GHD	total load profile business/commerce/services

3.2.2.4 Building insulation

It is assumed that efficiency level 1 which is the minimum standard of the Energy Saving Ordinance 2014 (EnEV 2014) can be met with the help of various insulation measures [TobiasLoga.2015]. Typical U-values as well as standard values for the status quo of buildings in depending on the year of construction are listed in Tab. 3.16.

Table 3.16: Assumed status quo U-values $W/(m^2 \cdot K)$ depending on the year of construction of individual buildings. Uniform values were used for all building types. Standard values for SFB from [TobiasLoga.2015] are used as a reference. *These values are assumed to be equivalent to the EnEV 2014 efficiency level 1 value.

year of construction	gable roof	flat	outer wall	windows
until 1859	2.60	2.60	2.00	2.80
1860 - 1918	1.30	1.30	1.70	2.80
1919 - 1948	1.40	1.40	1.70	2.80
1949 - 1957	1.40	1.40	1.40	2.80
1958 - 1968	0.80	0.80	1.00	2.80
1969 - 1978	0.50	0.50	1.00	2.80
1979 - 1983	0.50	0.50	0.80	4.30
1984 - 1994	0.40	0.40	0.50	3.20
1995 - 2001	0.35	0.35	0.30	1.90
2002 - 2009	0.35*	0.25	0.30	1.40
2010 - 2015	0.35*	0.21*	0.28	1.30
since 2016	0.35*	0.21*	0.22*	1.10
EnEV 2014 efficiency level 1	0.35	0.21	0.22	0.825

The U-value for windows is to be set for the following window area:

$$A_{\text{windows}} = f_w \cdot \text{NF} \cdot \text{GFA} \quad (3.15)$$

A_{windows}	window surface
f_w	window surface factor
NF	number of floors
GFA	gross floor area

A standard window surface factor f_w of 0.2 is assumed [62]. The U-value for the outer wall is to be set for the following wall area:

$$A_{\text{wall}} = U_{\text{building}} \cdot h_{\text{wall}} \cdot \text{NF} - A_{\text{windows}} \quad (3.16)$$

A_{wall}	wall surface
U_{building}	building scope
h_{wall}	floor height
NF	number of floors
A_{windows}	window surface

Typical values of h_{wall} for residential buildings are usually between 2.5 and 3.0 m [63]. For this study, a value of 2.7 m is assumed. The area of doors is neglected.

The U-value for the roof is to be set either for

$$A_{\text{gable roof}} = \text{NFA} \cdot \frac{1}{\cos(\alpha)} \quad (3.17)$$

$A_{\text{gable roof}}$	roof surface
NFA	net floor area
α	roof angle

or for

$$A_{\text{flat roof}} = \text{NFA} \quad (3.18)$$

$A_{\text{flat roof}}$	roof surface
NFA	net floor area

in dependency, if its a flat or a gable roof. The roof angle α is assumed to be a standard value of 30°. The data needed for this study were taken from the Level of Detail (LoD) 2 data set NF, roof type and municipal data NFA [64].

Tab. 3.16 shows U-values U_{yoc} depending on the year of construction of individual buildings. The goal is to achieve EnEV 2014 efficiency level 1 as U-value U_{new} . The difference between both is ΔU and is calculated with Eq. 3.19.

$$\Delta U = U_{\text{new}} - U_{\text{yoc}} \quad (3.19)$$

ΔU	U-value difference
U_{new}	EnEV 2014 U-value
U_{yoc}	year of construction U-value

Eq. 3.20 calculates the maximal temperature differences over the time steps at which the outdoor temperature T_{outdoor} drops below the heating limit temperature T_{limit} . The typical indoor temperature T_{indoor} is 20 °C according to DIN 18599 [63].

$$\Delta T_{\text{max}} = \max(T_{\text{indoor}} - T_{\text{outdoor}}) \quad T_{\text{limit}} > T_{\text{outdoor}} \quad (3.20)$$

ΔT_{\max}	maximal temperature difference
T_{indoor}	indoor temperature
T_{outdoor}	outdoor temperature

Next, ΔU is multiplied by the component surface (window, wall, roof) A_{comp} and ΔT_{\max} to calculate the potential heating power savings \dot{Q}_{savings} .

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{savings}} = \Delta U \cdot A_{\text{comp}} \cdot \Delta T_{\max} \quad (3.21)$$

\dot{Q}_{savings}	potential heating power savings
ΔU	U-value difference
A_{comp}	component surface
ΔT_{\max}	maximal temperature difference

Variable costs: No variable costs apply.

Periodical costs: Periodical costs are calculated with Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values of Tab. 3.17.

Table 3.17: Investment costs of energy saving measures [TobiasLoga.2015, 65, 66].

Outer wall: external thermal insulation composite system.

Windows: triple glazed.

measures	investment costs in €/m ²		x	y in a
outer wall	$C_I = 2.8102 \cdot x + 96.882$	insulation thickness	12 cm	50
gable roof	$C_I = 2.7738 \cdot x + 151.01$	insulation thickness	18 cm	50
flat roof	$C_I = 4.1087 \cdot x + 104.14$	insulation thickness	12 cm	50
windows	$C_I = 474.33 \cdot x^{-0.222}$	surface per window	1.5 m ² /pc.	40

Variable/periodical emissions: Since there is no operation within this component no variable emissions apply. [67] considered a carbon footprint of thermal insulation per surface unit (1 m²), for $U = 0.20 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ K})$. [68] considers different thicknesses. For a thickness of 15 cm, he calculates similar results for polystyrene as [67]. [65] considered different cost findings in order to create an equation. The most common materials were polystyrene for outer walls, mineral fiber or polyurethane for roofs.

Table 3.18: Emission costs of energy saving measures [67, 68].

measures	material	emissions in kg CO ₂ /m ²	comment
outer wall	polystyrene	11.8	expanded polystyrene (EPS)
	mineral fiber	5.6	glass wool low density (high densities leads to emissions about 20 kg CO ₂ /m ²)
gable roof	mineral fiber	5.6	glass wool low density (high densities leads to emissions about 20 kg CO ₂ /m ²)
	polyurethane	22.9	
flat roof		14,3	considered like gable roof (mean value of both materials)

[69] considered in his work triple glazed windows (1 650 mm · 1 300 mm) with central vertical separation. The inert gases (Tab. 3.19) fill the cavity of the triple glazed window. Electricity from the European electricity mix is used in the production of the windows [69].

Table 3.19: Emission costs of triple glazed windows [69]. Differentiation based on the frame material (polyvinylchloride (PVC) and aluminum is produced from bauxite ore).

frame material	inert gas	emissions in kg CO ₂ /unit	calculated emissions in kg CO ₂ /m ²
PVC	argon	205	96
	krypton	396	185
	xenon	1 896	884
PVC recycled	argon	194	90
Aluminum	argon	502	234
	krypton	692	323
	xenon	2 192	1 022
Aluminum recycled	argon	407	190
Timber	argon	108	50
	krypton	299	139
	xenon	1 799	839

We chose window with a PVC frame and the inert gas argon as an average window. We normalized the emissions of the 2.145 m² window to 1 m².

3.2.3 Transformers

3.2.3.1 Gasheating system

Variable costs: The operation of a heating system does not cause variable costs, which have to be allocated to the transformer component. Costs for the required natural gas are taken into account by the natural gas import (Sec. 3.2.1.2), electricity costs for the operation of feed water pumps and similar tasks are covered by the electricity load profiles.

Periodical costs: Periodical costs are calculated with Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values of Tab. 3.20. The annual operation costs C_{O_a} are calculated with Eq. 3.4.

Table 3.20: Values for calculating periodical costs.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	18	a		[29]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	1 005	€/kW		[16]
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	3	%/a		[29]

Variable/periodical emissions: We consider cumulative GHG emissions per kWh of heat produced, according to the GEMIS scenario “Gas-Heizung-Brennwert-DE-2020” [14].

Efficiency: [70] experimentally investigate the performance of a condensing boiler (25 kW nominal output) in real operating conditions. The mean efficiency of different modes is $\eta_B = 0.92$.

3.2.3.2 Central gas heating plant

Variable costs: The operation of a heating system does not cause variable costs, which have to be allocated to the transformer component. Costs for the required natural gas are taken into account by the natural gas import (Sec. 3.2.1.2).

Periodical costs: Periodical costs are calculated with Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values of Tab. 3.21. The annual operation costs C_{O_a} are calculated with Eq. 3.4.

Table 3.21: Values for calculating periodical costs.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	20	a		
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	143	€/kW	type: “Gas-HW-mittel-DE-2020”	[14]
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	2	%/a		[29]

Variable/periodical emissions: We consider cumulative GHG emissions of 264 g CO₂-equivalents per kWh of heat supplied, according to the GEMIS scenario “Gas-HW-gross-DE-2020” [14].

Efficiency: Assumed to be identical to those of *gas heating systems*. Therefore a mean efficiency of $\eta_B = 0.92$ (gas input / heat output) can be assumed [70].

3.2.3.3 District heat house station

Variable costs: No variable costs apply.

Periodical costs: The periodical costs are calculated with Eq. 3.2, Eq. 3.5, and Eq. 3.4 using the values of Tab. 3.38.

Table 3.22: Values for calculating periodical costs.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	20	a		[71]
rate of interest	i	4	%		
investment costs	C_I	835	€/kW	converted from periodical costs of 85 €/kW · a with $i = 8$ %/a and $y = 20$ a, using Eq. 3.2	[71]
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	3	%/a		[29]

Variable/periodical emissions: Negligible, especially compared to emissions from combustion per kWh [72].

Efficiency: Since the thermal losses of the heat exchanger lie within the thermal building envelope and amount to only a few percent, they are neglected.

3.2.3.4 Electric radiator

Variable costs: No variable costs apply. Costs for electricity are taken into account via the corresponding electricity source.

Periodical costs: The total periodical costs are calculated with Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values given in Tab. 3.23. We compared current electric radiators available on the German market (design capacity of 2 kW) to get typical investment costs. The annual operation costs are calculated using Eq. 3.4.

Table 3.23: Values for calculating periodical costs.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	15	a		[29]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	210	€/kW	comparison of commercially available devices	
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	2	%/a		[29]

variable/periodical emissions: For the heating type “El-Heizung-DE-2020-mix”, GHG emissions of 4.46 g/kWh are calculated with GEMIS [14]. Emissions for the provision of electricity was excluded, since the associated emissions are considered with the provision of electricity in the model applied here. Taking into account a number of full load hours of 1600 h/a, the periodic emissions for this component are 7 136 g/kWh.

Efficiency: Efficiency of electric radiators can be estimated as 1 [73].

3.2.3.5 Combined heat and power plant

Variable costs: No variable costs apply. Costs for fuels are considered with the respective sources.

Periodical costs: The annual operation costs are calculated using Eq. 3.4. The total annual costs are calculated using Eq. 3.2. Required values are listed in Tab. 3.38.

Table 3.24: Values for calculating periodical costs.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	15	a		[29]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	760	€/kW	for $P_{D,el} = 200$ kW	[74]
operation costs factor	f_{O_a}	8	%/a		[29]
typical design capacity	$P_{D,el}$	200	kW		assumption

Variable/periodical emissions: Through life cycle assessments, all emissions, including periodical emissions, are considered with the components variable emissions.

Gemis [14], for example, gives values for certain CHP units with certain efficiency ratios $\frac{\eta_{el}}{\eta_{th}}$. Two examples are given in Tab. 3.25.

If no precise values for specific CHPs are available, the efficiencies can be used for the following simplified calculation:

$$m'_{el} = \left(1 - \frac{\eta_{el}}{\eta_{el} + \eta_{th}}\right) \cdot (m'_{el,ref} + m'_{th,ref}) \quad (3.22)$$

$$m'_{th} = \left(1 - \frac{\eta_{th}}{\eta_{el} + \eta_{th}}\right) \cdot (m'_{el,ref} + m'_{th,ref}) \quad (3.23)$$

m'_{el}	specific emissions per electric output
m'_{th}	specific emissions per thermal output
$m'_{el,ref}$	specific reference emissions per electric output
$m'_{th,ref}$	specific reference emissions per thermal output
η_{el}	electric efficiency
η_{th}	thermal efficiency

Table 3.25: Example GHG emission values of two CHP units with 500 kW output (used scenarios: “Gas-BHKW-500-DE-2015” an “Biogas-Mais-0LUC-BHKW-GM 500 kW-DE-2015”) [14]. For the biogas CHP, fuel based on corn, one consideration of the Indirect Land Use Change Effect (ILUC) was taken into account. Additionally adapted values for deviating efficiencies calculated based on Eq. 3.22 and Eq. 3.23 are given.

	natural gas chp	biogas chp	ref.
η_{el}	0.3077	0.3169	[14]
η_{th}	0.6923	0.6831	[14]
$m_{el,ref}$ in g/kWh	410	163	[14]
$m_{th,ref}$ in g/kWh	164	74	[14]
η'_{el}	0.3746	0.3873	[74]
η'_{th}	0.5761	0.5627	Eq. 3.25
$m'_{el,ref}$ in g/kWh	347	140	Eq. 3.22
$m'_{th,ref}$ in g/kWh	225	97	Eq. 3.23

Efficiency: The electric efficiency for a CHP unit with a design capacity $P_{D,el} = 200$ kW can be assumed to be $\eta_{el} = 0.37$.

The thermal efficiency η_{th} can be calculated with the power-to-heat ratio σ , which is the “ratio of electricity from co-generation to useful heat when operating in full co-generation mode using operational data of the specific unit” [75]. The CHP utilization potential η_{KWK}^{Pot} can be assumed to 0.95 [76]. It can be calculated as follows [77]:

$$\sigma = \frac{\eta_{el}}{\eta_{KWK}^{Pot} - \eta_{el}} \quad (3.24)$$

σ	power-to-heat ratio
η_{el}	electric efficiency
η_{KWK}^{Pot}	CHP utilization potential

Subsequently, the thermal efficiency can be determined as follows [75]:

$$\eta_{th} = \frac{\eta_{el}}{\sigma} \quad (3.25)$$

η_{th}	thermal efficiency
σ	power-to-heat ratio
η_{el}	electrical efficiency

3.2.3.6 Heat pumps

In this section, heat pumps with different heat sources are considered. A differentiation is made between:

- air source heat pump (ASHP)
- ground-coupled heat pump (GCHP)
- groundwater heat pump (GWHP)
- surface water heat pump (SWHP)

Periodical costs (ASHP): The investments costs can be assumed depending on the design capacity P_D as well as an additional factor f_P , considering costs for planning, peripheral components (heat exchanger, storage tank, piping) and installation of the heat pump system, which is usually between 1.5 and 2.0 [78, 79]:

$$C_{I,ASHP} = 1520.7 \cdot P_D^{-0.363} \cdot f_P \quad (3.26)$$

$C_{I,ASHP}$ investment costs ASHP
 P_D design capacity
 f_P additional factor

The total periodical costs are calculated with Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values given in Tab. 3.26.

Table 3.26: Values for calculating periodical costs of ASHP.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	18	a		[29]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	1 318	€/kW	decentralized, $f_P = 2.0$	Eq. 3.26
investment costs	C_I	572	€/kW	centralized, $f_P = 2.0$	Eq. 3.26
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	2.5	%/a		[29]
typical design capacity	P_D	10	kW	decentralized	[78, 79]
typical design capacity	P_D	100	kW	centralized	assumption

Periodical costs (GCHP): The investments costs can be assumed depending on the design capacity P_D as well as an additional factor f_P , considering costs for planning, peripheral components (heat exchanger, storage tank, piping) and installation of the heat pump system, which is usually between 1.5 and 2.0 [78, 79]:

$$C_{I,GCHP} = 2\,610.2 \cdot P_D^{-0.558} \cdot f_P \quad (3.27)$$

$C_{I,GCHP}$ investment costs GCHP
 P_D design capacity
 f_P additional factor

The total periodical costs are calculated with Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values given in Tab. 3.27.

Table 3.27: Values for calculating periodical costs of decentralized GCHP.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	20	a		[29]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	1 444	€/kW	decentralized, $f_P = 2.0$	Eq. 3.27
investment costs	C_I	400	€/kW	centralized, $f_P = 2.0$	Eq. 3.27
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	2.5	%/a		[29]
typical design capacity	P_D	10	kW	decentralized	[78, 79]
	P_D	100	kW	centralized	[78, 79]

Periodical costs (GWHP): The investments costs can be assumed depending on the design capacity P_D as well as an additional factor f_P , considering costs for planning, peripheral components (heat exchanger, storage tank, piping) and installation of the heat pump system, which is usually between 1.5 and 2.0 [78, 79]:

$$C_{I,GWHP} = 2\,717.1 \cdot P_D^{-0.435} \cdot f_P \quad (3.28)$$

$C_{I,GWHP}$	investment costs GWHP
P_D	design capacity
f_P	additional factor

The total periodical costs are calculated with Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values given in Tab. 3.27.

Table 3.28: Values for calculating periodical costs of decentralized GWHP.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	20	a		[29]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	1 996	€/kW	$f_P = 2.0$	Eq. 3.28
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	2.5	%/a		[29]
typical design capacity	P_D	10	kW		[78, 79]

Periodical costs (SWHP): For simplicity, it is assumed that the cost of SWHP is the same as the GWHP. Both heat pumps are open systems, use water as a heat source and require a secondary loop.

The lower capacity limit for central heat pumps can be assumed to be 100 kW [80]. Specific investment costs stagnate as the nominal heating capacity increases, so the specific investment costs for larger systems are therefore comparable [80].

Table 3.29: Values for calculating periodical costs of SWHP.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	20	a		[29]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	733	€/kW	$f_P = 2.0$	Eq. 3.28
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	2.5	%/a		[29]
typical design capacity	P_D	100	kW	as the power increases, the specific costs remain almost constant	[78, 79]

Variable/periodical emissions: For a ASHP (solid-wall construction) with a capacity of 16.3 kW, according to Johnson [81], 485 kg CO_{2,eq.} are accounted for the production of the heat pump and 1 604 kg CO_{2,eq.} for the production of the refrigerant (R410A). Johnson [81] assumed a lifetime of 15 years, therefore the periodic emissions amount to 8 544 $\frac{\text{g CO}_{2,\text{eq.}}}{\text{kWh}\cdot\text{a}}$. While for old heat pumps further greenhouse gas emissions have to be considered due to the Leakage of refrigerants, this is not the case for modern heat pumps [80]. We assume that comparable values can be applied to the remaining heat pumps.

Variable costs: No variable costs apply. Costs for electricity are taken into account via the corresponding electricity source.

Efficiency: The coefficient of performance is modeled for every time step of the model, depending on the current temperature of the heat source (Sec. 3.3). To determine the coefficient of performance COP of a real machine, a quality grade η is applied to the Carnot coefficient of performance COP_{Carnot} [82]:

$$COP = COP_{\text{Carnot}} \cdot \eta \quad (3.29)$$

COP	coefficient of performance
COP_{Carnot}	Carnot coefficient of performance
η	quality grade

Table 3.30: Quality grade of heat pumps [83].

heat pump	η
ASHP	0,40
GCHP	0,55
GWHP	0,50

According to [84], the quality grade of large heat pumps is between 0.4 and 0.6, so a value of $\eta = 0,5$ is assumed for SWHP in the following [84]. To take the loss of efficiency into account when the heat exchanger ices up, a temperature limit is defined. As soon as the heat source temperature reaches this value, the COP drops by the icing factor κ .

For ASHP, a limit temperature of 2 °C is set. If the air temperature falls below this limit, the evaporator ices up, so that energy is required for the defrosting process and the COP drops by the icing factor of $\kappa = 0.8$ [85].

$$COP_{\text{practical}} = COP_{\text{Carnot}} \cdot \eta \cdot \kappa \quad (3.30)$$

$COP_{\text{practical}}$	practical coefficient of performance
COP_{Carnot}	Carnot coefficient of performance
η	quality grade
κ	icing factor

Further parameters: The potential of GCHP is limited by the available area. This limitation is taken into account by the extraction rate of the borehole heat exchangers. The extraction rate in monovalent system operation is determined according to VDI directive 4640 sheet 2 as $32.8 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}}$ for a borehole heat exchanger. The extraction rate is determined by the region specific thermal conductivity, which is assumed to be $2 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}\cdot\text{K}}$ in Herne, for example. The extraction rate is based on 2400 full load hours per year and an output temperature of -3 °C at peak load [86]. A borehole length of 100 m is assumed for the geothermal probes and a minimum area A_{min} of 100 m^2 . A_{min} is calculated based on the distances in Tab. 3.31.

Table 3.31: Distances that have to be considered when using close-to-surface (depths up to 100 m) geothermal energy. [86–89].

distance to	probe	collector	well
property line	5 m	1 m	10 m
among each other	6 m	0,2 - 0,7 m	20 m
buildings	2 m	2 m	2 m

The open spaces A_{open} are areas that are not developed or contaminated by inherited waste. Furthermore, the distances from Tab. 3.31 are taken into account. All restrictions contribute to the reduction of the potential area. The calculations are performed with geographic information system (GIS) operations.

$$P_{\text{max_probe}} = \frac{A_{\text{open}}}{A_{\text{min}}} \cdot l_{\text{probe}} \cdot p_{\text{probe}} \quad (3.31)$$

$P_{\text{max_probe}}$	maximum heat extraction of the probes
A_{open}	open space
A_{min}	minimum area per probe
l_{probe}	length of the probe
p_{probe}	heat extraction per meter probe length

We assumed a radiator supply temperature of 60 °C, since we had to consider an old building construction average in Herne. If the buildings are newer or if more precise data on the buildings are available, this value can be adjusted on a building-specific basis [90].

3.2.3.7 Electrolysis

Variable costs: No variable costs apply. Costs for electricity are taken into account via the corresponding electricity source.

Periodical costs: Periodical costs are calculated with Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values of Tab. 3.32. The annual operation costs $C_{O,a}$ are calculated with Eq. 3.4.

Table 3.32: Values for calculating periodical costs of electrolysis.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	20	a		[91]
rate of interest	i	4	%		sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	800	€/kW		[92]
operation costs	$C_{O,a}$	18	€/(kW a)		[93]
typical design capacity	P_D	100	MW		[93]

Variable/periodical emissions: All emissions were related to the volume of hydrogen produced by means of life cycle assessment. The cumulative emissions are 43 g CO₂ equivalents per kg. of hydrogen produced [18]. With an energy content of 33.33 kWh/kg hydrogen, this results in variable emissions of 1.3 g CO₂/kWh. It is assumed that the CO₂ released during the fuel cell was captured in the methanization process. To simplify matters, both variable emission values are therefore set to zero.

Efficiency: According to Schmidt [93], efficiencies of

- 75 - 85 % for proton exchange membrane electrolysis, and
- 77 % for alkaline electrolysis

may be scheduled. We assume the mean value of 78.5 %.

3.2.3.8 Methanization

Variable costs: A range of 100 to 300 €/t is given for the supply of CO₂ [91]. We assume the mean value of 150 €/t (calorific value of methane 55,5 MJ/kg).

Periodical costs: Periodical costs are calculated with Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values of Tab. 3.33. The annual operation costs C_{O_a} are calculated with Eq. 3.4.

Table 3.33: Values for calculating periodical costs.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	20	a		[91]
rate of interest	i	4	%		sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	800	€/kW	chemical methanization, related to electrical input	[94]
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	1	%/a		assumption

Variable/periodical emissions: For this component, no literature values could be collected on the emissions associated with production/installation/maintenance. For this reason, a accumulated variable emission value of 10 g/kWh is assumed, based on other technical systems. Operating electricity has been excluded from the balance sheet, as this is taken into account elsewhere in the model.

Efficiency: Efficiency of methanization can be assumed as max. 83 % [95, 96].

3.2.3.9 Fuel cell

variable costs: No variable costs apply. Costs for fuels are considered with the respective sources.

Periodical costs: Periodical costs are calculated with Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values of Tab. 3.34. The annual operation costs C_{O_a} are calculated with Eq. 3.4. The investment costs for a fuel cell (low temperature proton exchange membrane fuel cell) on district level are around 1.3 M €/MW [97]. The annual operation costs amount to 95 000 €/MW/a and therefore to 7.3 %/a of the investment costs.

Table 3.34: Values for calculating periodical costs of a low temperature proton exchange membrane fuel cell.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	10	a		[97]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	1 300	€/kW		[97]
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	7.3	%/a		[97]

Variable/periodical emissions: For this component, no literature values could be collected on the emissions associated with production/installation/maintenance. For this reason, a cumulated variable emission value of 10 g/kWh is assumed, based on other comparable technical systems. Operating electricity has been excluded from the balance sheet, as this is taken into account elsewhere in the model. According to [19], there are no other variable emissions.

Efficiency: The considered reference system are polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell (PEMFC). The electrical efficiency is 40 %, the overall efficiency is 90 % [19].

3.2.4 Storages

3.2.4.1 Central thermal storage

Variable costs: Variable costs (e.g., for the operation of pumps) are neglected due to simplification purposes (see Sec. 3.1.4).

Periodical costs: Periodical costs are calculated with Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values of Tab. 3.35.

Table 3.35: Values for calculating periodical costs.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	20	a		[21]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	35	€/kWh	mean value from	[21]
operation costs	$C_{O,a}$	0.16	€/kWh/a	calculated based on	[98]
typical design capacity	P_D	500 - 5 5000	kWh		[21]

variable emissions: Variable emissions apply for the operation of pumps, etc. required electricity. Due to the storage model structure used, these are neglected in the model.

Periodical emissions: According to [20], for a sensitive thermal storage with a capacity of 4 820 kWh/a, annual emissions of 3 580 kg/a can be estimated for the construction of the storage. This is equivalent to 743 g/kWh/a.

Efficiency: The efficiency of the storage cycle is 98 % plus 3 % storage losses per day [21] (equals to 0.125 %/h).

Further parameters: In a reference project in Heidelberg, a loading and unloading capacity of 10 MW is available for a 40 MWh storage facility [22]. This corresponds to an in- and outflow ratio of 0.25.

3.2.4.2 Building heat storage

Variable costs: Variable costs (e.g., for the operation of pumps) are neglected due to simplification purposes (Sec. 3.1.4).

Periodical costs: According to [99], a 1 100 l combination storage tank (heating and drinking water) costs about 2 000 - 3 000 €. Assuming that the temperature spread ΔT is 40 K, this reference storage tank thus has a capacity Q of

$$Q = m \cdot c_{p,w} \cdot \Delta T = 1\,100 \text{ kg} \cdot 4.185 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg} \cdot \text{K}} \cdot 40 \text{ K} = 184\,140 \text{ kJ} = 51.15 \text{ kWh}. \quad (3.32)$$

Q storage capacity
 m fluid mass
 $c_{p,w}$ specific heat capacity (water)
 ΔT temperature spread

With an averaged cost assumption (2 500 €), the specific investment costs result to 49 €/kWh. The total periodical costs are calculated with Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values of Tab. 3.36.

Table 3.36: Values for calculating periodical costs.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	20	a		[29]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	49	€/kWh	[99], Eq. 3.32	
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	1	%/a		[29]

Variable/periodical emissions: No variable emissions apply. According to [100], 278 kg of CO₂ is released for the production of a 500 l steel storage tank. Assuming that the temperature spread is 40 K, this reference storage tank thus has a capacity Q of

$$Q = m \cdot c_{p,w} \cdot \Delta T = 500 \text{ kg} \cdot 4.185 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg} \cdot \text{K}} \cdot 40 \text{ K} = 83\,700 \text{ kJ} = 23.25 \text{ kWh}, \quad (3.33)$$

Q	storage capacity
m	fluid mass
$c_{p,w}$	specific heat capacity (water)
ΔT	temperature spread

and with a lifetime of 20 a specific periodic emissions of 604 g/kWh.

Efficiency: Following the *central thermal storage*, we assume an efficiency of the storage cycle of 0.98. Furthermore, we assume, from the data sheet of the reference system “Aqua Espresso III 1000” [23], storage losses of 0.2 %/h. outflow = 1

Further parameters Further parameters required for the modeling of a building heat storage are listed in Tab. 3.37. Capacity inflow and outflow indicate the performance with which the storage can be charged or discharged.

Table 3.37: Further technical specifications of an building heat storage system

property	value	ref.
capacity max.	1	assumption
capacity min.	0	assumption
capacity inflow	1	[23]
capacity outflow	1	[23]

3.2.4.3 Battery storage

Variable costs: No variable costs apply.

Variable/periodical costs: The total periodical costs are calculated with Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values given in Tab. 3.38. The annual operation costs are calculated using Eq. 3.4.

Table 3.38: Values for calculating periodical costs.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
decentral battery storages					
component lifetime	y	20	a		[101]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	1 000	€/kWh	$P_D = 19.5 \text{ kWh}$	[102]
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	1.5	%/a		[103]
central battery storages					
component lifetime	y	20	a		[101]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_I	1 071	€/kWh	$P_D = 100\text{-}300 \text{ kWh}$	[104]
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	1.0	%/a		[104]

Variable/periodical emissions: No variable emissions apply. Mean values for lithium ion storage are given in [24] and can be estimated of 22 kg per MJ storage capacity. This leads to the periodical emissions $3\,960 \text{ g CO}_2/(\text{kWh} \cdot \text{a})$.

Efficiency: Overall efficiency including injection, storage and withdrawal of a reference system is 98 % [25].

Further parameters: Manufacturer specifications of a typical home battery system are used as a reference which are given in Tab. 3.39. Efficiency, min./max. capacity as well as min/max inflow and outflow values are considered for central battery storages as well. Capacity inflow and outflow indicate the performance with which the storage can be charged or discharged.

Table 3.39: Further technical specifications of an exemplary battery storage system [25].

property	value
capacity max.	1
capacity min.	0.1
capacity inflow	0.77
capacity outflow	0.71

3.2.4.4 Hydrogen storage

Variable costs: Variable costs apply for the operation of pumps, etc. required electricity. Due to the storage model structure used, these are neglected in the model.

Periodical costs: Calculation due to eq. Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values of table Tab. 3.40.

Table 3.40: Values for calculating periodical costs.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	30	a		[27]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
investment costs	C_1	17.68	€/kW		[27]
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	2	%/a		[27]

According to [27] the investment costs for a steel cylinder storage with a capacity of 509 kg hydrogen are around 300 000 €. With an energy content of 33.33 kWh/kg hydrogen, this results in a storage capacity of 16 965 kWh. Thus, specific investment costs of 17.68 €/kWh results.

Variable emissions: Variable emissions apply for the operation of pumps, etc. required electricity. Due to the storage model structure used, these are neglected in the model.

Periodical emissions: According to [26], the production emissions of various hydrogen storage systems are given. We adopt the mean value of 9 600 kg per kWh storage capacity. Based on a service life of 30 a (see above), this results in periodic emissions of 320 g/kWh/a.

Efficiency The cycle efficiency can be assumed to be 100 % [27]. Daily losses of 0.06 %/d for frequent use apply, 1.5 %/d for no use [19]. We assume a mean value of 0.78 %/d.

Further parameters No references could be found for the capacity min./max., so assumptions were made. Capacity inflow and outflow indicate the performance with which the storage can be charged or discharged.

Table 3.41: Further technical specifications of an exemplary battery storage system [25]

Property	Value	ref.
capacity max.	1	assumption
capacity min.	0	assumption
capacity inflow	1	[27]
capacity outflow	1	[27]

3.2.4.5 Natural gas storage

Since natural gas storage facilities are generally similar in design to hydrogen storage facilities, the parameters of the hydrogen storage facility are adopted.

3.2.5 Links

3.2.5.1 Building heat system

Heat losses within building (from the heat supply technology to final heat demand) are neglected, with regard to model simplification in the sense of urban energy system modeling [105]. For the same reason, costs and emissions for the building-internal supply are neglected in the model.

3.2.5.2 District heat network

Variable costs: Similar to the operation of thermal storages, the modeling methodology does not take into account operating energy (e.g., for pumps). Since this only accounts for a small proportion of the transported energy, it is neglected.

Periodical costs: Periodical costs depend on the diameter of a district heating pipeline. They are calculated with Eq. 3.2 and Eq. 3.5 using the values from Tab. 3.42 and Tab. 3.43.

Table 3.42: Total investment costs for district heat pipes, layed in streets [106].

nominal diameter	inv. costs		nominal diameter	inv. costs	
	in €/m	in €/(m · a)		in €/m	in €/(m · a)
DN20	391	64	DN80	616	101
DN25	396	65	DN100	760	125
DN32	422	69	DN125	913	150
DN40	437	72	DN150	1101	181
DN50	495	81	DN200	1311	215
DN65	537	88	DN250	1755	288

Since there is no linear cost-structure, the investment decisions between the different pipe-diameters is realized using mixed-integer decisions. Therefore, for every pipe section a decision is made whether every pipe diameter is implemented or not. Since a two-pipe system is considered, the pipes must be mutually exclusive, so only one diameter can be implemented per pipe section.

Table 3.43: Values for calculating periodical costs.

name	sym.	value	unit	comment	ref.
component lifetime	y	60	a		[71]
rate of interest	i	4	%		Sec. 3.1.1
operation cost factor	f_{O_a}	12	%/a		[71]

Variable/periodical emissions: Similar to the variable costs, no variable emissions are considered. Fröling et al. [107] are giving emissions released for the installation of three different pipe diameters. The values are shown in Tab. 3.44.

Table 3.44: Carbon dioxide emissions for the installation of different district heating pipe diameters according to Fröling et al. [107].

DN	CO ₂ emissions in kg/(6 m)
25	88
100	380
500	4300

Therefrom, the following quadratic approximation function can be derived, which calculates the specific emissions per pipe meter $m'_{CO_2,m}$ in dependency from the pipe diameter d :

$$m'_{CO_2,m} = 0.0124351 \cdot d^2 + 2.33895 \cdot d + 21.7544 \quad (3.34)$$

From this, the values listed in Tab. 3.45 can be calculated, taking into account a service life of 60 years (Tab. 3.43).

Table 3.45: Approximated carbon dioxide emissions for the installation of different district heating pipe diameters. Calculated using Eq. 3.34.

diameter d in mm	periodical emissions in $\frac{g}{m \cdot a}$	diameter d diameter	periodical emissions in $\frac{g}{m \cdot a}$
20	204	250	3844
25	244	300	5118
32	304	400	8186
40	376	450	9979
50	472	500	11944
65	629	600	16394
80	801	700	21534
100	1056	800	27365
125	1412	900	33887
150	1812	1000	41099
200	2742		

Efficiency: The losses are calculated according to the numerical Eq. 3.35, where the average temperature of the medium $T_{DH-medium}$ is assumed to be 90 °C, which corresponds to an operating temperature level (flow temperature/return temperature) of 120 °C/60 °C. The temperature of the ground T_{ground} at the installation depth is simplified to be a constant 8 °C.

$$Q_{loss} = (T_{DH-Medium} - T_{Ground}) \cdot (0.16805 \cdot \ln(\phi) + 0.85684) \quad (3.35)$$

Q_{loss}	annual losses of one meter pipe (in kWh/(m · a))
$T_{\text{DH-medium}}$	average temperature of the medium
T_{ground}	ground temperature
\varnothing	nominal diameter of the considered pipe (in m)

Table 3.46: Annual losses of one meter district heating pipe as a function of diameter calculated with Eq. 3.35.

DN	losses in kWh/(m · a)	DN	losses in kWh/(m · a)
20	16.35281178	250	51.15760507
25	19.42775223	300	53.67001436
32	22.82950879	400	57.63430209
40	25.90444925	450	59.2573641
50	28.9793897	500	60.70924254
65	32.5947955	600	63.22165182
80	35.45608671	700	65.34586361
100	38.53102716	800	67.18593955
125	41.60596761	900	68.80900156
150	44.1183769	1000	70.26088
200	48.08266462		

The medium velocity is calculated with Eq. 3.36 [108].

$$v = 0.4834 + 4.7617 \cdot (\varnothing^{0.3701}) \quad (3.36)$$

- v velocity (in m/s)
 \varnothing nominal diameter of the considered pipe (in m)

The maximum transportable heat flow is calculated with Eq. 3.37 [108], where the heat capacity of water $c_{p,w}$ is simplified to a constant 4 182 J/(kg · K), and the density ρ is set to 965.31 kg/m³ [109].

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{max,DN}} = (T_{\text{F}} - T_{\text{R}}) \cdot c_{p,w} \cdot \rho \cdot \frac{\pi}{4} \varnothing \cdot v \quad (3.37)$$

$\dot{Q}_{\text{max,DN}}$	maximum transportable heat flow
T_{F}	flow temperature of the district heating network
T_{R}	return temperature of the district heating network
$c_{p,w}$	heat capacity of the district heating medium (water)
ρ	density of the district heating medium (water)
\varnothing	nominal diameter of the considered pipe (in mm)
v	velocity

The conversion of losses per meter can be done with Eq. 3.38, therefore the full load hours are set to 1 500 h/a [71] and the maximum transportable heat flow is calculated with Eq. 3.37.

$$\dot{q}_{\text{loss}} = \frac{Q_{\text{loss}}}{1\,500 \frac{\text{h}}{\text{a}} \cdot \dot{Q}_{\text{max,DN}}} \quad (3.38)$$

\dot{q}_{loss}	specific loss capacity
Q_{loss}	annual losses of one meter pipe
$\dot{Q}_{\text{max,DN}}$	maximum transportable heat flow

Table 3.47: Relative losses of one meter of district heating pipe as a function of diameter and installed capacity calculated with Eq. 3.38.

DN	losses in $10^{-5}\text{kW}/(\text{m} \cdot \text{kW})$	DN	losses in $10^{-5}\text{kW}/(\text{m} \cdot \text{kW})$
20	22.52751837	250	0.121173592
25	14.87470458	300	0.081435436
32	9.20637537	400	0.043397078
40	5.889801491	450	0.033513325
50	3.73412616	500	0.026586689
65	2.166160585	600	0.017797094
80	1.400355839	700	0.012667098
100	0.872632724	800	0.009430953
125	0.541834493	900	0.007267688
150	0.36625277	1000	0.005755183
200	0.196732308		

The applied district heating approach can handle the annual losses (Tab. 3.46) as well as the specific losses (Tab. 3.47), the choice is up to the energy system creator.

3.2.5.3 Electricity exchange

Variable costs: The following variable costs are incurred for the exchange of electricity via the public power grid:

$$\text{variable costs} = \text{network charges} + \text{EEG fees} + \text{concession fees} \quad (3.39)$$

Table 3.48: Considered costs for the calculation of variable costs for Sec. 3.2.5.3.

	value	unit	ref.
network charges	0.0542	€/kWh	[110]
EEG fees	0.065	€/kWh	[111]
concession fees	0.0199	€/kWh	[110]

Periodical costs: Periodic costs for the connection to the power grid are not considered, as it is assumed that these are already covered by the regular purchase of electricity (Sec. 3.2.1.1).

Variable/periodical emissions: No emissions apply for the exchange of electricity between individual subsystems.

3.3 Weather data

Weather data (temperature, global horizontal irradiation, diffuse horizontal irradiation, wind-speed) provided by the German Meteorological Service (DWD) are used [112]. The closest weather station to this investigation is “Düsseldorf Airport” [113], about 43 km from the investigated areas. The historical data set of 2012 is used, which was an almost perfectly average year with respect to the sun duration [114].

For the applied modeling approach the direct horizontal irradiance $dirhi$ is required, which can be calculated from the given global horizontal irradiation ghi and the diffuse horizontal irradiation dhi [5]:

$$dirhi = ghi - dhi \quad (3.40)$$

dirhi direct horizontal irradiance
ghi global horizontal irradiation
dhi diffuse horizontal irradiation

Furthermore, the radiation data E_s are given as time-summed energy quantity in J per m² per 10 minutes. Unit conversions into watts per square meter is required and carried out followingly [5]:

$$[E_s] = \frac{\text{J}}{\text{cm}^2 \cdot 10\text{min}} = \frac{\text{Ws}}{\frac{1}{10\,000} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot 600\text{ s}} = \frac{50}{3} \cdot \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}^2} \quad (3.41)$$

As ground temperature, a constant value of 13.7 °C can be assumed throughout the year for the study area, according to [80] (based on [115]).

The temperature of rivers ϑ_w within the investigation area can be assumed to depend on the air temperature ϑ_a as follows [80]:

$$\vartheta_w = 1.0349 \cdot \vartheta_a + 1.4346 \quad (3.42)$$

ϑ_w river temperature
 ϑ_a air temperature

Acronyms

ASHP air source heat pump

BDEW German Association of Energy and Water Industries

BMBF German Federal Ministry of Education and Research

CO₂ carbon dioxide

CHP combined heat and power

DWD German Meteorological Service

EEG 2021 Renewable Energies Act 2021

EnEV 2014 Energy Saving Ordinance 2014

KWKG 2020 Combined Heat and Power Act 2020

GCHP ground-coupled heat pump

GEMIS Global Emission Model of Integrated Systems

GHG greenhouse gas

GIS geographic information system

GWHP groundwater heat pump

LoD Level of Detail

MFB multi family building

oemof Open Energy Modelling Framework

PVC polyvinylchloride

PV photovoltaic

R2Q RessourcenPlan im Quartier

SFB single family building

SWHP surface water heat pump

SESMG Spreadsheet Energy System Model Generator

Acknowledgements

The authors thank the BMBF for funding the R2Q project under grant number 033W102A.

References

- [1] C. Klemm and P. Vennemann. “Modeling and optimization of multi-energy systems in mixed-use districts: A review of existing methods and approaches”. In: *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 135 (2021), p. 110206. ISSN: 13640321. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2020.110206 (cit. on p. 4).
- [2] G. Mavrotas. “Effective implementation of the ϵ -constraint method in Multi-Objective Mathematical Programming problems”. en. In: *Applied Mathematics and Computation* 213.2 (July 2009), pp. 455–465. ISSN: 00963003. DOI: 10.1016/j.amc.2009.03.037. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0096300309002574> (visited on 08/27/2021) (cit. on p. 4).
- [3] C. Klemm, P. Vennemann, J. Budde, and G. Becker. *The spreadsheet energy system model generator — spreadsheet energy system model generator latest documentation*. URL: <https://spreadsheet-energy-system-model-generator.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> (visited on 01/25/2022) (cit. on p. 5).
- [4] S. Hilpert, C. Kaldemeyer, U. Krien, S. Günther, C. Wingenbach, and G. Plessmann. “The open energy modelling framework (oemof) - A new approach to facilitate open science in energy system modelling”. In: *Energy Strategy Reviews* 22 (2018), pp. 16–25. ISSN: 2211467X. DOI: 10.1016/j.esr.2018.07.001 (cit. on p. 5).
- [5] C. Klemm. “Modelling and optimization of multi-energy systems in mixed-use districts: an exemplary application”. MA thesis. Münster: FH Münster, Mar. 2020 (cit. on pp. 7, 51, 52).
- [6] Verein Deutscher Ingenieure (VDI). *Cumulative energy demand (KEA) - terms, definitions, methods of calculation*. VDI 4600. VDI Verlag, 2012 (cit. on pp. 8, 11, 12).
- [7] A. Breitkopf. *Haushalte - Strompreise in Deutschland bis 2019*. 2021. URL: <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/154908/umfrage/strompreise-fuer-haushaltskunden-seit-2006/> (visited on 07/20/2021) (cit. on pp. 20, 25).
- [8] A. Breitkopf. *Haushalte - Strompreise in Deutschland bis 2019*. 2021. URL: <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/38897/umfrage/co2-emissionsfaktor-fuer-den-strommix-in-deutschland-seit-1990/> (visited on 09/02/2021) (cit. on p. 20).
- [9] Bundesverband Wärmepumpe (BWP). *Position zur Strompreisgestaltung*. Berlin, 2020. URL: https://www.waermepumpe.de/fileadmin/user_upload/waermepumpe/07_Publikationen/Sonstige/2020-07-20_Position_zur_Strompreisgestaltung.pdf (visited on 08/19/2021) (cit. on p. 20).
- [10] A. Breitkopf. *Strompreise für Gewerbe- und Industriekunden in Deutschland bis 2019*. 2021. URL: <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/154902/umfrage/strompreise-fuer-industrie-und-gewerbe-seit-2006/> (visited on 07/20/2021) (cit. on p. 20).
- [11] A. Breitkopf. *Entwicklung der Gaspreise für Haushaltskunden in Deutschland in den Jahren 2010 bis 2020*. 2021. URL: <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/168286/umfrage/entwicklung-der-gaspreise-fuer-haushaltskunden-seit-2006/> (visited on 07/20/2021) (cit. on pp. 20, 25).
- [12] A. Breitkopf. *Gaspreise für Gewerbe- und Industriekunden in Deutschland in den Jahren 2010 bis 2020*. 2021. URL: <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/168528/umfrage/gaspreise-fuer-gewerbe--und-industriekunden-seit-2006/> (visited on 12/10/2019) (cit. on p. 20).
- [13] P. Sivabalasingam. “Fortschreibung des Energiekonzeptes für ein Quartier mit Hilfe des Open Energy Modelling Frameworks”. MA thesis. Steinfurt: FH Münster, 2021 (cit. on p. 20).

- [14] IINAS GmbH – Internationales Institut für Nachhaltigkeitsanalysen und -strategien. *GEMIS-Datenbank*. 2019. URL: <http://iinas.org/gemis-download-121.html> (visited on 12/02/2019) (cit. on pp. 20, 21, 25, 26, 36–39).
- [15] K. Mertens. *Photovoltaik: Lehrbuch zu Grundlagen, Technologie und Praxis*. München: Fachbuchverlag Leipzig im Carl Hanser Verlag, 2018 (cit. on pp. 20, 26).
- [16] M. Gaderer, R. Kunde, and H. Spliethoff. “Systemuntersuchungen an Heizungsanlagen: Holzpelletkessel, Heizöl-Brennwert- und Erdgas-Brennwertkessel im Vergleich”. In: *BWK Energie* 59 (2007), pp. 39–46. URL: <https://mediatum.ub.tum.de/doc/1161256/file.pdf> (visited on 08/30/2021) (cit. on pp. 20, 36).
- [17] M. Kaltschmitt, W. Streicher, and A. Wiese, eds. *Erneuerbare Energien*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2013. ISBN: 978-3-642-03248-6 978-3-642-03249-3 (cit. on p. 20).
- [18] E. Cetinkaya, I. Dincer, and G. Naterer. “Life cycle assessment of various hydrogen production methods”. en. In: *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 37.3 (Feb. 2012), pp. 2071–2080. ISSN: 03603199. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2011.10.064. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S036031991102430X> (visited on 09/06/2021) (cit. on pp. 20, 43).
- [19] J. Töpler and J. Lehmann, eds. *Wasserstoff und Brennstoffzelle*. de. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2014. ISBN: 978-3-642-37414-2 978-3-642-37415-9. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-37415-9. URL: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-642-37415-9> (visited on 09/15/2021) (cit. on pp. 20, 44, 47).
- [20] S. Guillén-Lambea, M. Carvalho, M. Delgado, and A. Lazaro. “Sustainable enhancement of district heating and cooling configurations by combining thermal energy storage and life cycle assessment”. en. In: *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy* 23.3 (Apr. 2021), pp. 857–867. ISSN: 1618-954X, 1618-9558. DOI: 10.1007/s10098-020-01941-9. URL: <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10098-020-01941-9> (visited on 09/14/2021) (cit. on pp. 20, 45).
- [21] A. Seitz, S. Zunft, and C. Hoyer-Klick. *Technologiebericht 3.3b energiespeicher (thermisch, thermo-chemisch und mechanisch) innerhalb des forschungsprojekts TF energiewende*. de. Tech. rep. Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt, 2018. URL: https://epub.wupperinst.org/frontdoor/deliver/index/docId/7056/file/7056_Energiespeicher.pdf (visited on 09/13/2021) (cit. on pp. 20, 45).
- [22] A. Kraft. *Großwärmespeicher – Bausteine der Energiewende*. July 2018. URL: https://enerko.de/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/181026-W%C3%A4rmespeicher_Kraft.pdf (visited on 09/14/2021) (cit. on pp. 20, 45).
- [23] Ritter Energie- und Umwelttechnik GmbH & Co. KG and Digma. *Aqua Espresso III*. 2020. URL: <https://mam-prod.paradigma.de/pinaccess/pinaccess.do?pinCode=7C92GD9FOEYJ> (visited on 09/16/2021) (cit. on pp. 20, 46).
- [24] M. C. McManus. “Environmental consequences of the use of batteries in low carbon systems: The impact of battery production”. In: *Applied Energy* 93 (2012), pp. 288–295. ISSN: 03062619. DOI: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2011.12.062 (cit. on pp. 21, 47).
- [25] E3/DC GmbH. *S10 E Technische Daten*. 2019. URL: https://www.e3dc.com/pdf/ch/E3DC_Technische-Daten_E.pdf (visited on 01/29/2020) (cit. on pp. 21, 47, 48).
- [26] P. Adametz, C. Pötzinger, S. Müller, K. Müller, M. Preißinger, R. Lechner, D. Brüggemann, M. Brautsch, and W. Arlt. “Thermodynamic Evaluation and Carbon Footprint Analysis of the Application of Hydrogen-Based Energy-Storage Systems in Residential Buildings”. en. In: *Energy Technology* 5.3 (Mar. 2017), pp. 495–509. ISSN: 21944288. DOI: 10.1002/ente.201600388. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/ente.201600388> (visited on 09/17/2021) (cit. on pp. 21, 47).

- [27] Klaus Stolzenburg, Martin Wietschel, Fabio Genoese, Julia Michaelis, Jochen Lehmann, Andreas Miede, Stephan Krause, Christian Sponholz, Sabine Donadei, Fritz Crotogino, and Andreas Acht. “Integration von Wind-Wasserstoff-Systemen in das Energiesystem”. de. In: (2014), p. 250. URL: https://www.tib.eu/de/suchen?tx_tibsearch_search%5Baction%5D=download&tx_tibsearch_search%5Bcontroller%5D=Download&tx_tibsearch_search%5Bdocid%5D=TIBKAT%3A872792943&cHash=8a6162d8e3ca544a1e02575d5619fdc9#download-mark (visited on 09/16/2021) (cit. on pp. 21, 47, 48).
- [28] Deutscher Bundestag. *Gesetz für den Ausbau erneuerbarer Energien (ErneuerbareEnergien-Gesetz - EEG 2021)*. 2021 (cit. on pp. 21, 30).
- [29] Verein Deutscher Ingenieure (VDI). *VDI 2067 Blatt 1 - Wirtschaftlichkeit gebäudetechnischer Anlagen: Grundlagen und Kostenberechnung*. Berlin, September 2012 (cit. on pp. 23, 26, 31, 36–38, 40, 41, 45).
- [30] W. R. Institute. “The greenhouse gas protocol - A corporate accounting and reporting standard”. en. In: (2004). URL: <https://ghgprotocol.org/sites/default/files/standards/ghg-protocol-revised.pdf> (cit. on p. 24).
- [31] V. Wesselak and S. Voswinckel. *Photovoltaik – Wie Sonne zu Strom wird*. Technik im Fokus. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2016. ISBN: 978-3-662-48905-5 978-3-662-48906-2 (cit. on pp. 25, 27).
- [32] A. Breitkopf. *Preisentwicklung für eine fertig installierte Solaranlage* in Deutschland in den Jahren 2008 bis 2018*. 2019. URL: <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/156490/umfrage/preis-fuer-eine-fertig-installierte-solaranlage-in-deutschland/> (visited on 12/18/2019) (cit. on p. 25).
- [33] J. Kratochvil, W. Boyson, and D. King. *Photovoltaic array performance model*. Tech. rep. SAND2004-3535, 919131. Aug. 2004, SAND2004–3535, 919131. DOI: 10.2172/919131. URL: <https://www.osti.gov/servlets/purl/919131/> (visited on 07/21/2022) (cit. on p. 26).
- [34] Oemof Developer Group. *Feedinlib*. Jan. 2022. URL: <https://feedinlib.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> (visited on 12/02/2019) (cit. on p. 26).
- [35] Regionalverband Ruhr. *Regionales Solardachkataster*. 2022. URL: <https://www.rvr.ruhr/themen/oekologie-umwelt/startseite-klima/solardachkataster/> (visited on 01/21/2022) (cit. on pp. 26, 27).
- [36] P. Kloth. *Kosten Solarthermie - das kostet die Solaranlage*. 2022. URL: <https://www.energieheld.de/solaranlage/solarthermie/kosten> (visited on 01/24/2022) (cit. on p. 26).
- [37] V. Wesselak, T. Schabbach, T. Link, and J. Fischer. *Regenerative Energietechnik*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2013 (cit. on pp. 26, 27).
- [38] Deutsches Institut für Normung (DIN). *DIN EN 12975-2:2006-06 - Thermische Solaranlagen und ihre Bauteile - Kollektoren - Teil 2: Prüfverfahren; Deutsche Fassung EN 12975-2:2006*. 2006 (cit. on p. 27).
- [39] T. Lauf, M. Memmler, and S. Schneider. *Emissionsbilanz erneuerbarer Energieträger: Bestimmung der vermiedenen Emissionen im Jahr 2018*. 2019. URL: https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/1410/publikationen/2019-11-07_cc-37-2019_emissionsbilanz-erneuerbarer-energien_2018.pdf (cit. on p. 27).
- [40] R. Corradini and M. Sutter. “Heizen mit Sonnenwärme: Mehr als nur warmes Wasser”. In: *Energiewirtschaftliche Tagesfragen* 62 (2012), pp. 69–72 (cit. on p. 27).
- [41] H. Meier, C. Fünfgeld, T. Adam, and B. Schieferdecker. *Repräsentative VDEW-Lastprofile: VDEW Materialien*. Ed. by Verband Deutscher Elektrizitätswirtschaft. Cottbus, 1999. URL: https://www.bdew.de/media/documents/1999_Repraesentative-VDEW-Lastprofile.pdf (cit. on p. 28).

- [42] Energienetz Mitte. *Standardlastprofilverfahren*. 2019. URL: <https://www.energienetz-mitte.de/marktpartner/netzzugang-nutzung/strom/standardlastprofilverfahren/> (visited on 10/30/2019) (cit. on p. 28).
- [43] A. Breitkopf. *Jährlicher Stromverbrauch eines 1-Personen-Haushalts in Deutschland nach Gebäudetyp im Jahr 2019*. 2019. URL: <https://de-statista-com.ezproxy.fh-muenster.de/statistik/daten/studie/558239/umfrage/stromverbrauch-einen-1-personen-haushalts-in-deutschland/> (visited on 08/17/2021) (cit. on p. 28).
- [44] A. Breitkopf. *Jährlicher Stromverbrauch eines 2-Personen-Haushalts in Deutschland nach Gebäudetyp im Jahr 2019*. 2019. URL: <https://de-statista-com.ezproxy.fh-muenster.de/statistik/daten/studie/558277/umfrage/stromverbrauch-einen-2-personen-haushalts-in-deutschland/> (visited on 08/17/2021) (cit. on p. 28).
- [45] A. Breitkopf. *Jährlicher Stromverbrauch eines 3-Personen-Haushalts in Deutschland nach Gebäudetyp im Jahr 2019*. 2019. URL: <https://de-statista-com.ezproxy.fh-muenster.de/statistik/daten/studie/558280/umfrage/stromverbrauch-einen-3-personen-haushalts-in-deutschland/> (visited on 08/17/2021) (cit. on p. 28).
- [46] A. Breitkopf. *Jährlicher Stromverbrauch eines 4-Personen-Haushalts in Deutschland nach Gebäudetyp im Jahr 2019*. 2019. URL: <https://de-statista-com.ezproxy.fh-muenster.de/statistik/daten/studie/558288/umfrage/stromverbrauch-einen-4-personen-haushalts-in-deutschland/> (visited on 08/17/2021) (cit. on p. 28).
- [47] A. Breitkopf. *Jährlicher Stromverbrauch eines 5-Personen-Haushalts in Deutschland nach Gebäudetyp im Jahr 2019*. 2019. URL: <https://de-statista-com.ezproxy.fh-muenster.de/statistik/daten/studie/558295/umfrage/stromverbrauch-einen-5-personen-haushalts-in-deutschland/> (visited on 08/17/2021) (cit. on p. 28).
- [48] S. Herne. *Statistisches Jahrbuch 2018 - Herne in Zahlen*. Tech. rep. Sept. 2020. URL: <https://www.herne.de/PDF/Stadtfakten/Statistik/Jahrbuch%202018/Statistisches-Jahrbuch-2018.pdf> (visited on 02/09/2021) (cit. on p. 28).
- [49] Deutsches Institut für Normung (DIN). *DIN 277 - Areas and volumes in building construction*. 2021 (cit. on p. 28).
- [50] Verein Deutscher Ingenieure (VDI). *VDI 3807 Part 2 - Characteristic consumption values for buildings Characteristic heating-energy, electrical-energy and water consumption values*. Tech. rep. 2014 (cit. on pp. 29, 32).
- [51] Statista. *Stromverbrauch je Quadratmeter Verkaufsfläche im deutschsprachigen Einzelhandel in den Jahren 2013 und 2015*. 2015. URL: <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/372110/umfrage/stromverbrauch-je-quadratmeter-verkaufsflaeche-im-deutschsprachigen-einzelhandel/> (visited on 12/05/2019) (cit. on p. 29).
- [52] S. Ahrens. *Durchschnittliche Verkaufsfläche je Filiale ausgewählter Vertriebslinien im Lebensmitteleinzelhandel in Deutschland im Jahr 2019*. Sept. 2020. URL: <https://de-statista-com.ezproxy.fh-muenster.de/statistik/daten/studie/202106/umfrage/durchschnittliche-verkaufsflaeche-deutscher-lebensmitteleinzelhaendler/> (visited on 08/09/2021) (cit. on p. 29).
- [53] Bundesnetzagentur. *EEG-Registerdaten und -Fördersätze*. 2021. URL: https://www.bundesnetzagentur.de/DE/Sachgebiete/ElektrizitaetundGas/Unternehmen_Institutionen/ErneuerbareEnergien/ZahlenDatenInformationen/EEG_Registerdaten/EEG_Registerdaten_node.html (visited on 07/20/2021) (cit. on p. 30).
- [54] Deutscher Bundestag. “Gesetz für die Erhaltung, die Modernisierung und den Ausbau der Kraft-Wärme-Kopplung – KWKG”. In: (2014), pp. 33–40. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-658-07554-5_3. (Visited on 02/14/2020) (cit. on pp. 30, 31).

- [55] B. Thomas. *Mini Blockheizkraftwerke*. Würzburg: Vogel Buchverlag, 2007. ISBN: 9783834330697 (cit. on p. 31).
- [56] G. Schaumann and K. Schmitz. *Kraft-Wärme-Kopplung*. Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag, 2010. ISBN: 9783642014253 (cit. on p. 31).
- [57] A. Breitkopf. *Börsenstrompreis am EPEX-Spotmarkt für Deutschland/Luxemburg von Juni 2020 bis Juni 2021*. 2021. URL: <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/289437/umfrage/strompreis-am-epex-spotmarkt/> (visited on 07/20/2021) (cit. on p. 31).
- [58] U. Bigalke, Y. Zhang, J. Kunde, M. Schmitt, Y. Zeng, H. Discher, K. Bensmann, and C. Stolte. *Der dena-gebäudereport 2015. statistiken und analysen zur energieeffizienz im gebäudebestand*. Berlin: Deutsche Energie-Agentur GmbH (dena), 2015. URL: https://www.voltimum.de/sites/www.voltimum.de/files/pdflibrary/8162_dena-gebaeudereport_2015_pdf1.pdf (cit. on p. 32).
- [59] Zensus. *Gebäude und Wohnungen sowie Wohnverhältnisse der Haushalte: Kreisfreie Stadt Herne*. Ed. by Information und Technik Nordrhein-Westfalen. 2011. URL: <https://www.it.nrw/sites/default/files/gemeindebl%C3%A4tter/G05916.pdf> (visited on 04/06/2022) (cit. on p. 32).
- [60] BDEW Bundesverband der Energie- und Wasserwirtschaft e.V, Verband kommunaler Unternehmen e.V. (VKU), and Groupement Européen des entreprises et Organismes de Distribution d'Énergi. *BDEW/VKU/GEODE-Leitfaden - Abwicklung von Standardlastprofilen Gas*. Tech. rep. URL: <https://www.enwg-veroeffentlichungen.de/badtoelz/Netze/Gasnetz/Netzbeschreibung/LF-Abwicklung-von-Standardlastprofilen-Gas-20110630-final.pdf> (visited on 12/02/2019) (cit. on p. 33).
- [61] M. Hellwig. *Entwicklung und Anwendung parametrisierter Standardlastprofile: doctor thesis*. München: TU München, 2003. URL: <https://mediatum.ub.tum.de/doc/601557/601557.pdf> (visited on 12/02/2019) (cit. on p. 33).
- [62] O. B. Assmann. “Bestimmung des stündlichen Wärmebedarfs von Wohngebäuden auf der Basis lokaler Wetterdatensätze, unter Zuhilfenahme der DIN 4108”. Bachelor thesis. FH Muenster, 2020 (cit. on p. 34).
- [63] Deutsches Institut für Normung (DIN). *DIN18599.2018 - Energy efficiency of buildings – Calculation of the net, final and primary energy demand for heating, cooling, ventilation, domestic hot water and lighting: Part 1: General balancing procedures, terms and definitions, zoning and evaluation of energy*. 2018 (cit. on p. 34).
- [64] Bezirksregierung Koeln. *LoD2 - Gebäudemodell*. 2022. URL: https://www.bezreg-koeln.nrw.de/brk_internet/geobasis/3d_gebaeudemodelle/index.html (visited on 07/15/2022) (cit. on p. 34).
- [65] Eberhard Hinz and Institut Wohnen und Umwelt. *Kosten energierelevanter Bau- und Anlagenteile bei der energetischen Modernisierung von Altbauten*. Ed. by Institut Wohnen und Umwelt. 2015. URL: https://www.iwu.de/fileadmin/publikationen/handlungslogiken/2015_IWU_Hinz_Kosten-energierelevanter-Bau-und-Anlagenteile-bei-der-energetischen-Modernisierung-von-Altbauten.pdf (visited on 08/30/2021) (cit. on p. 35).
- [66] Bundesministerium des Innern, für Bau und Heimat (BMI). *BNB Nutzungsdauern von Bauteilen: Bewertungssystem Nachhaltiges Bauen*. Ed. by Bundesministerium des Innern, für Bau und Heimat. 2017. URL: https://www.nachhaltigesbauen.de/fileadmin/pdf/Nutzungsdauer_Bauteile/BNB_Nutzungsdauern_von_Bauteilen_2017-02-24.pdf (visited on 08/31/2021) (cit. on p. 35).
- [67] R. Kunič. “Carbon footprint of thermal insulation materials in building envelopes”. In: *Energy Efficiency* 10.6 (2017), pp. 1511–1528. ISSN: 1570-646X. DOI: 10.1007/s12053-017-9536-1 (cit. on p. 35).

- [68] J. Michalak, S. Czernik, M. Marcinek, and B. Michałowski. “Environmental burdens of External Thermal Insulation Systems. Expanded Polystyrene vs. Mineral Wool: Case Study from Poland”. In: *Sustainability* 12.11 (2020), p. 4532. DOI: 10.3390/su12114532 (cit. on p. 35).
- [69] Raya Yousef Teenou. “Energy and CO2 emissions associated with the production of Multi-glazed windows”. Master Thesis. Östersund: Mid Sweden University, 2012. URL: <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:532125/FULLTEXT01.pdf> (visited on 09/08/2021) (cit. on p. 36).
- [70] D. T. Bălănescu and V. M. Homutescu. “Experimental investigation on performance of a condensing boiler and economic evaluation in real operating conditions”. In: *Applied Thermal Engineering* 143 (2018), pp. 48–58. ISSN: 13594311. DOI: 10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2018.07.082 (cit. on pp. 36, 37).
- [71] Der Energieeffizienzverband für Wärme, Kälte und KWK e. V. (AGFW). *Wirtschaftlichkeit nach §§20 und 24 KWKG - Verfahren zur Darlegung der Finanzierungsücke bei Neu- und Ausbau von Wärme-/Kältenetzen und Wärme-/Kältespeichern in Deutschland*. Tech. rep. AGFW, Oct. 2020. URL: <https://www.fw704.de/hauptmenue> (visited on 04/03/2022) (cit. on pp. 37, 49, 50).
- [72] F. Neirotti, M. Noussan, and M. Simonetti. “Evaluating the emissions of the heat supplied by district heating networks through A life cycle perspective”. en. In: *Clean Technologies* 2.4 (Oct. 2020), pp. 392–405. ISSN: 2571-8797. DOI: 10.3390/cleantechnol2040024. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2571-8797/2/4/24> (visited on 07/29/2021) (cit. on p. 37).
- [73] F. Gentgen. *Heizen mit Strom: Energieverschwendung oder besser als sein Ruf?* Ed. by Agentur für Erneuerbare Energien. 2017. URL: <https://www.unendlich-viel-energie.de/themen/waerme/heizen-mit-strom-energieverschwendung-oder-besser-als-sein-ruf> (visited on 07/18/2022) (cit. on p. 38).
- [74] ASUE Arbeitskreis Brennstoffzellen/BHKW. *BHKW-Kenndaten 2014/2015: Module, Anbieter, Kosten*. Ed. by ASUE Arbeitsgemeinschaft für sparsamen und umweltfreundlichen Energieverbrauch e.V. 2014 (cit. on pp. 38, 39).
- [75] European Parliament and of the Council, ed. *Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council*. 2012. URL: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2012/27/2021-01-01> (visited on 09/08/2021) (cit. on p. 39).
- [76] P. Vennemann. *Kraft-Wärme-Kopplung (Lecture Script)*. FH Münster, Apr. 2021 (cit. on p. 39).
- [77] Der Energieeffizienzverband für Wärme, Kälte und KWK e. V. (AGFW), ed. *Arbeitsblatt FW 308: Certification of CHP plants - Determining the CHP electricity*. 2015. URL: <https://www.agfw.de/energiewirtschaft-recht-politik/energiende-politik/effizienz-kwk/fw-308-kwk-prozess/> (visited on 09/08/2021) (cit. on p. 39).
- [78] S. Wolf. *Integration von Wärmepumpen in industrielle Produktionssysteme : Potenziale und Instrumente zur Potenzialerschließung*. 2017. DOI: 10.18419/OPUS-9593 (cit. on pp. 40, 41).
- [79] S. Wolf. *Analyse des Potenzials von Industrierärmepumpen in Deutschland : Forschungsbericht : Endbericht*. 2014. DOI: 10.2314/GBV:84567675X (cit. on pp. 40, 41).
- [80] J. Budde. *Wärmepumpen in stadtquartieren - untersuchung anhand eines quartiers in herne*. Bachelor Thesis. Münster, Sept. 2020 (cit. on pp. 41, 52).
- [81] E. P. Johnson. “Air-source heat pump carbon footprints: HFC impacts and comparison to other heat sources”. In: *Energy Policy* 39.3 (2011), pp. 1369–1381. ISSN: 03014215. DOI: 10.1016/j.enpol.2010.12.009 (cit. on p. 41).
- [82] Oemof Developer Group. *oemof thermal*. 2022. URL: <https://oemof-thermal.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> (visited on 07/18/2022) (cit. on p. 42).

- [83] ETG Taskforce Wärmemarkt. *Potenziale für Strom im Wärmemarkt bis 2050: Wärmeversorgung in flexiblen Energie-versorgungssystemen mit hohen Anteilen an erneuerbaren Energien: Studie der Energietechnischen Gesellschaft im VDE (ETG)*. Ed. by VDE Verlag. 2015. URL: https://www.energiesdialog2050.de/BASE/DOWNLOADS/VDE_ST_ETG_Warmemarkt_RZ-web.pdf (visited on 08/19/2020) (cit. on p. 42).
- [84] C. Arpagaus. *Hochtemperatur-Wärmepumpen: Marktübersicht, Stand der Technik und Anwendungspotenziale*. Neuerscheinung. Berlin and Offenbach: VDE Verlag GmbH, 2019. ISBN: 9783800745517. URL: https://www.content-select.com/index.php?id=bib_view&ean=9783800745517 (cit. on p. 42).
- [85] J. Launer, F. Pleissner, C. Möller, J. Wolf, M.-C. Gering, P. Schönfeldt, U. Krien, C. Kaldemeyer, and S. Günther. *oemof/oemof-thermal: Amazing Absorption*. 2020. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3606384 (cit. on p. 42).
- [86] Verein Deutscher Ingenieure (VDI). *Thermische Nutzung des Untergrunds Erdgekoppelte Wärmepumpenanlagen*. Vol. 27.080. VDI 4640 Blatt 2. Berlin: Beuth Verlag GmbH, 2019 (cit. on p. 42).
- [87] Verein Deutscher Ingenieure (VDI). *Thermische Nutzung des Untergrunds - Grundlagen, Genehmigungen, Umweltaspekte Betrieb*. Vol. 27.010, 27.080, 27.200. VDI 4640 Blatt 1. Berlin: Beuth Verlag GmbH, Juni 2010 (cit. on p. 42).
- [88] Landesamt für Natur, Umwelt und Verbraucherschutz Nordrhein-Westfalen. *Wasserwirtschaftliche Anforderungen an die Nutzung von oberflächennaher Erdwärme: LANUV-Arbeitsblatt 39*. Recklinghausen, 2019. URL: https://www.lanuv.nrw.de/fileadmin/lanuvpubl/4_arbeitsblaetter/LANUV_Arbeitsblatt_39.pdf (visited on 09/01/2020) (cit. on p. 42).
- [89] D. P. Boon, G. J. Farr, C. Abesser, A. M. Patton, D. R. James, D. I. Schofield, and D. G. Tucker. “Groundwater heat pump feasibility in shallow urban aquifers: Experience from Cardiff, UK”. In: *The Science of the total environment* 697 (2019), p. 133847. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.133847 (cit. on p. 42).
- [90] I. Staffell, D. Brett, N. Brandon, and A. Hawkes. “A review of domestic heat pumps”. In: *Energy & Environmental Science* 5.11 (2012), p. 9291. ISSN: 1754-5692. DOI: 10.1039/c2ee22653g (cit. on p. 43).
- [91] Martin Wietschel. “Integration erneuerbarer Energien durch Sektorkopplung: Analyse zu technischen Sektorkopplungsoptionen”. de. In: (2019), p. 334. URL: https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/1410/publikationen/2019-03-12_cc_03-2019_sektrokopplung.pdf (cit. on pp. 43, 44).
- [92] T. Smolinka. “Studie: IndWEDe Industrialisierung der Wasserelektrolyse in Deutschland: Chancen und Herausforderungen für nachhaltigen Wasserstoff für Verkehr, Strom und -Wärme”. de. In: (2018), p. 201 (cit. on p. 43).
- [93] T. Schmidt. *Wasserstofftechnik: Grundlagen, Systeme, Anwendung, Wirtschaft*. de. München: Hanser, 2020. ISBN: 978-3-446-46001-0 (cit. on p. 43).
- [94] M. Thema, F. Bauer, and M. Sterner. “Power-to-Gas: Electrolysis and methanation status review”. en. In: *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 112 (Sept. 2019), pp. 775–787. ISSN: 13640321. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2019.06.030. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S136403211930423X> (visited on 09/13/2021) (cit. on p. 44).
- [95] S. Bajohr, M. Götz, F. Graf, and F. Ortloff. “Speicherung von regenerativ erzeugter elektrischer Energie in der Erdgasinfrastruktur”. de. In: (2011), p. 11 (cit. on p. 44).
- [96] Christiane Golling, Reemt Heuke, Hannes Seidl, and Jeannette Uhlig. *Roadmap Power to gas*. 2017. URL: https://www.dena.de/fileadmin/dena/Publikationen/PDFs/2019/Roadmap_Power_to_Gas.pdf (cit. on p. 44).

- [97] Danish Energy Agency. *Data Sheet for Electricity and District Heat Production - Updated June 2022*. https://ens.dk/sites/ens.dk/files/Analyser/technology_data_for_el_and_dh.xlsx. Nov. 2022 (cit. on p. 44).
- [98] P. Rundel, B. Meyer, M. Meiller, I. Meyer, R. Daschner, M. Jakuttis, M. Franke, S. Binder, and A. Hornung. *Speicher für die energiewende*. Tech. rep. Fraunhofer Umsicht, 2013. URL: <https://www.um sicht.fraunhofer.de/de/presse-medien/pressemitteilungen/2013/studie-energiespeicher.html> (visited on 04/20/2022) (cit. on p. 45).
- [99] J. Piasecki. *Wärmespeicher - für Heizungen oder Solarthermie*. URL: <https://www.energieheld.de/waermespeicher> (visited on 08/15/2022) (cit. on p. 45).
- [100] P. Königsreuther. *Einzigartiger Wärmespeicher spart Ressourcen und CO2*. Ed. by MaschinenMarkt. 2020. URL: <https://www.maschinenmarkt.vogel.de/einzigartiger-waermespeicher-spart-ressourcen-und-co2-a-936042/> (visited on 07/18/2022) (cit. on p. 46).
- [101] K. Mertens. *Photovoltaik: Lehrbuch zu Grundlagen, Technologie und Praxis*. 6., aktualisierte und erweiterte Auflage. München: Hanser, 2022. ISBN: 9783446471948. DOI: Konrad (cit. on p. 46).
- [102] J. Figgenger, D. Haberschusz, K.-P. Kairies, O. Wessels, S. Zurmühlen, and D. U. Sauer. *Speichermonitoring BW: Jahresbericht 2019*. Ed. by Institut für Stromrichtertechnik und Elektrische Antriebe. 2019. URL: https://www.speichermonitoring-bw.de/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/Speichermonitoring_BW_Jahresbericht_2019_ISEA_RWTH_Aachen.pdf (visited on 07/18/2022) (cit. on p. 46).
- [103] J. Weniger, T. Tjaden, and V. Quaschnig. *Wirtschaftlichkeit von Batteriespeichern*. 2013. URL: <https://pv-speicher.htw-berlin.de/wp-content/uploads/2014/04/EKSH-2013-Wirtschaftlichkeit-von-Batteriespeichern-in-Kombination-mit-Photovoltaiksystemen.pdf> (visited on 02/04/2020) (cit. on p. 46).
- [104] J. Knoefel. *Technisch-ökonomische Bewertung von Quartierspeichern. Eine Betrachtung der Wirtschaftlichkeit und der regionalökonomischen Effekte von Quartierspeichern*. Tech. rep. 2021, p. 27. URL: https://www.ioew.de/fileadmin/user_upload/BILDER_und_Downloaddateien/Publikationen/2021/Knoefel_Herrmann_2021_Technisch_oekonomische_Bewertung_von_Quartierspeichern.pdf (visited on 08/15/2022) (cit. on p. 46).
- [105] R. Haas. “Energy efficiency indicators in the residential sector”. In: *Energy Policy* 25:7-9 (1997), pp. 789–802. ISSN: 03014215. DOI: 10.1016/S0301-4215(97)00069-4 (cit. on p. 48).
- [106] T. Nussbaumer and S. Thalmann. *Sensitivity of System Design on Heat Distribution Cost in District Heating*. en. Tech. rep. Zürich: Verenum AG, 2014, p. 38. URL: https://nachhaltigwirtschaften.at/resources/iea_pdf/reports/iea_bioenergy_task32_cost_analysis_district_heating.pdf (visited on 08/08/2022) (cit. on p. 48).
- [107] M. Fröling, C. Holmgren, and M. Svanström. “Life cycle assessment of the district heat distribution system: Part 1: pipe production”. en. In: *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 9.2 (Mar. 2004), pp. 130–136. ISSN: 0948-3349, 1614-7502. DOI: 10.1007/BF02978572. URL: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/BF02978572> (visited on 03/02/2022) (cit. on p. 49).
- [108] CSE Bristol. *Technical description of pipes parameters calculation in Thermos*. 2021. URL: <https://tool.thermos-project.eu/help/network/technical-description.html#pipe-diameter-calc> (visited on 04/29/2022) (cit. on p. 50).
- [109] Verein Deutscher Ingenieure (VDI). *VDI-Wärmeatlas: mit 320 Tabellen*. ger. Berlin Heidelberg, 2013 (cit. on p. 50).

- [110] Stadtwerke Herne. *Entgelte für den Netzzugang Strom*. 2021. URL: <https://www.stadtwerke-herne.de/netze/stromnetz/entgelte-netzzugang-strom> (visited on 07/23/2021) (cit. on p. 51).
- [111] Bundesnetzagentur. *EEG-Umlage 2021 beträgt 6,500 ct/kWh*. 2021. URL: https://www.bundesnetzagentur.de/SharedDocs/Pressemitteilungen/DE/2020/20201015_EEGUmlage.html (visited on 07/23/2021) (cit. on p. 51).
- [112] Deutscher Wetterdienst. *Climate data center*. July 2020. URL: <https://cdc.dwd.de/portal/202007291339/index.html> (cit. on p. 51).
- [113] Deutscher Wetterdienst. *Stationsliste der 78 Messstationen (nach Stationsname sortiert)*. 2022. URL: <https://www.dwd.de/DE/leistungen/klimadatendeutschland/stationsuebersicht.html> (visited on 07/02/2022) (cit. on p. 51).
- [114] Deutscher Wetterdienst. *Wetter und klima - deutscher wetterdienst - klimaüberwachung - deutschland - zeitreihen und trends*. 2022. URL: <https://www.dwd.de/DE/leistungen/zeitreihen/zeitreihen.html?nn=480164> (visited on 01/20/2022) (cit. on p. 51).
- [115] R. Bracke, W. Rocholl, B. Schmidt, G. Bussmann, T. Eicker, and B. Kelz. *Potenzialstudie Erneuerbare Energien NRW Teil 4 - Geothermie*. 2015. URL: https://www.lanuv.nrw.de/fileadmin/lanuvpubl/3_fachberichte/Fachbericht_40-Teil4-Geothermie_web.pdf (visited on 07/02/2022) (cit. on p. 52).